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Refugee Protection Greece Country report

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List of Abbreviations

AAU: Autonomous Asylum Units

AMEY: Anonymous Health Units

AIDA: Asylum Information Database

CEAS: Common European Asylum System

DRC: Danish Refugee Council

EASO: European Asylum Support Office

ECCHR: European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights

ECHR: European Court of Human Rights

EU: European Union

FRONTEX: European Border and Coast Guard Agency

FRS: First Reception Service

GAMM: Global Approach to Migration and Mobility

GCR: Greek Council of Refugees

GDP: Global Detention Project

IOM: International Organization for Migration

MOPOCP: Ministry of Citizen Protection

OHCHR: Human Rights Committee

RAO: Regional Asylum Office

RIC: Reception and Identification Centre

RIS: Reception and Identification Service

RSA: Refugee Support Aegean

TCN: Third Country Nationals

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

About the Project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU) its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP3, which focuses specifically on asylum procedures and refugee protection.

Executive Summary/Abstract

This report is part of the third Work Package of RESPOND (WP3) and deals with the issues of refugee protection and asylum procedures. The concept of “protection” is considered here as the ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors involved in the definition, conceptualisation and implementation of asylum procedures and refugee protection in the EU Member States. The main goal of this WP3 Greece report is to present and discuss both the legal framework and the implementation of refugee protection and asylum procedures in Greece in a timeframe from 2011 to 2018, focusing on the example of the island of Lesbos. It draws from empirical research evidence on existing practices and responses at the grassroots level and reflects on the experiences, perceptions and actions of actors and refugees by highlighting the main problems and difficulties in the implementation of international protection policies.

The political and social context of the period in question (2011-2018) is determined by both the multilevel socioeconomic recession in Greece and increased refugee arrivals. Furthermore, the aforementioned years bore witness to significant developments regarding refugee protection and asylum procedures. Apart from Law 3907/2011, which established for the first time the Asylum Service, the First Reception Service and the Appeals Authority, the increase in refugee arrivals was followed by the EU–Turkey Statement of 18th of March 2016 and the adoption of Law 4375/2016. These developments introduced a considerable number of changes in the institutional framework on asylum, refugee protection and the management of refugee flows through the implementation of the EU “Hotspot Approach”. Asylum applications in Greece increased significantly due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands, where Hotspots are established and where crucial protection issues are on a steady rise. Furthermore, it should also be mentioned that there has been a shift in the Greek political context since the writing of the previous reports on legal and policy framework (WP1) and border management (WP2). The recent national elections in Greece resulted in the electoral win of right-wing party “New Democracy” (ND). Since the beginning of its term in office, a wide range of measures on refugee issues have been – mostly – announced but also implemented. Additionally, the previously established Ministry of Migration Policy has been abolished as an independent ministry and is now the General Secretariat for Immigration Policy, Reception and Asylum, belonging to the Ministry of Citizen Protection and headed by an Alternate Minister of Citizen Protection “responsible for Migration Policy”. Even if these developments are not relevant for the 2011-2018 timeframe that this report focuses on, they corroborate and emphasise the temporary and fluid character of the investigated issues.

The research methodology implemented for the needs of this report – and of the overall RESPOND programme – combined diverse methods. A complementary review of the national legislation on issues of refugee protection was conducted for the purpose of the legal framework analysis. Additionally, the material gathered included reports by national and international organizations and NGOs, as well as European national official documents. The main section of this report, relating to the implementation of asylum procedures and refugee protection, is analysed on the basis

of the empirical material assembled during the implemented research. Specifically, field qualitative research was conducted in Lesvos and in Athens from June 2018 to December 2018 at a meso and micro level. The meso level included 15 semi-structured interviews with executives and employees of the authorities, international organizations and NGOs. Additionally, a round-table discussion organised by the University of the Aegean working group in November 2018 provided crucial insights to the research. As for the micro level, 34 semi-structured interviews were conducted with refugees living in Moria Hotspot and in Athens, including a focus-group interview. The qualitative analysis of the interview material was conducted using NVIVO software and organised on the basis of the RESPOND major research issues.

The report is divided into 5 sections, including introduction, methodology and conclusions. The third section presents the “Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework” – and, more specifically, the important developments since 2011 and the national legal and institutional framework regarding “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection”, drawing from the analysis of the WP1 Report on “Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance”. The following section, entitled “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions” constitutes the main core of this report. It draws from the research conducted for the needs of the RESPOND programme and discusses the practices, experiences and perceptions regarding the Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection. In particular, it discusses how refugees perceive the procedures of registration and Identification, asylum procedures, their experiences with actors, the legal assistance they may have received, psychosocial support and other forms of informal support, the living conditions in Moria Hotspot and issues of detention. Apart from the experiences and perceptions of refugees, insights from the narratives and practices of actors and stakeholders are also analysed.

The report concludes with crucial observations regarding the growing gap between the legal framework on protection and its implementation, as well as with reference to specific critical protection issues arising in the context of Greece and the island of Lesvos. In addition to the inadequate living conditions suffered by asylum-seekers who are forced to remain in the North-eastern Aegean islands, there is also a serious lack in security and in supporting services providing medical and psychosocial assistance, information regarding the asylum procedures and the rights of asylum-seekers, legal aid and legal representation. The conclusions also highlight differences in the implementation, experiences and practices applied in the field of refugee protection, which can vary depending on the site, the point in time and the actors involved. The report closes with certain policy recommendations that emerged as a result of the present research.

Introduction

This report is part of the third Work Package of RESPOND and deals with the issues of refugee protection and asylum procedures. The concept of “protection”, which is largely undefined, is considered here as “all activities aimed at obtaining full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and spirit of the relevant bodies of law, namely human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law” (UNHCR, 2011; European Commission, 2016). Additionally, protection is approached as both an objective and an activity, as both the right to survival and physical safety and the right to the enjoyment of a full range of rights (such as civil and political rights, freedom of movement, political participation and economic, social and cultural rights). As such, by the term “refugee protection” we refer to the ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors involved in the definition, conceptualisation and implementation of asylum procedures and refugee protection in the EU Member States.

The main goal of this WP3 Greece report is to present and discuss both the legal framework and the implementation of refugee protection and asylum procedures in Greece during the 2011-2018 period. Following the WP1 and WP2 reports that focused on the overview of the “Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance” and the “Border Management and Migration Controls in Greece” respectively, this report will concentrate mostly on the implementation of Refugee Protection. Thus, it will reflect mainly on the implementation and implications of the legal and institutional framework provided by the WP1 Greece report of RESPOND Project, and its summary in the present report. The analysis of the implementation of refugee protection is conducted on the basis of the gathered empirical research evidence on existing practices and responses at the grassroots level. Accordingly, the report reflects on the experiences, perceptions and actions of actors and refugees by highlighting the main problems and difficulties in the implementation of international protection policies.

The political and social context of the period in question (2011-2018) is determined by both the multilevel socioeconomic recession in Greece and increased refugee arrivals. The aforementioned years bore witness to significant developments regarding refugee protection and asylum procedures. Apart from Law 3907/2011, which established for the first time the Asylum Service, the First Reception Service and the Appeals Authority, the increase in refugee arrivals was followed by the EU–Turkey Statement of 18th of March 2016 and the adoption of Law 4375/2016. These developments introduced a considerable number of changes in the institutional framework on asylum, refugee protection and the management of refugee flows through the implementation of the EU “Hotspot Approach”. Asylum applications in Greece increased significantly due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands, where Hotspots are established and where crucial protection issues are on a steady rise.

It should also be mentioned that there has been a shift in the Greek political context since the writing of the previous reports. The recent national elections in Greece resulted in the electoral win of right-wing party “New Democracy” (ND). Since the beginning of its term in office, a wide range of measures on refugee issues have been – mostly – announced but also implemented. Examples of measures already

taken include sweep operations in refugee squats in the centre of Athens and the transfer of the refugees to camps located in remote mainland areas. Some of the announcements and future plans refer to the stricter securitisation of the Greek borders, the conversion of the camps to “closed centres”, etc. Additionally, the previously established Ministry of Migration Policy has been abolished as an independent ministry and is now the General Secretariat for Immigration Policy, Reception and Asylum, belonging to the Ministry of Citizen Protection and headed by an Alternate Minister of Citizen Protection “responsible for Migration Policy”. Even if these developments are not relevant for the 2011-2018 timeframe that this report focuses on, it is important they be mentioned as they corroborate and emphasise the temporary and fluid character of the investigated issues.

The report is divided into 5 sections, including introduction, methodology and conclusions. The third section presents the “Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework” – and, more specifically, important developments since 2011 – and the national legal and institutional framework regarding “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection”, drawing from the analysis of the WP1 Report on “Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance”. The following section, entitled “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions” constitutes the main core of this report. It draws from the research conducted for the needs of the RESPOND programme and discusses the practices, experiences and perceptions regarding the Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection. In particular, it discusses how refugees perceive the procedures of Registration and Identification, asylum procedures, their experiences with actors, the legal assistance they may have received, psychosocial support and other forms of informal support, the living conditions in Moria Hotspot and issues of detention. Apart from the experiences and perceptions of refugees, insights from the narratives and practices of actors and stakeholders are also analysed.

Methodology and Sources

The research methodology implemented for the needs of this report – and the overall RESPOND programme – combined diverse methods. Beyond the analysis provided in the WP 1 Greek report “Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance”, a complementary review of the national framework on issues of refugee protection was conducted for the section on the “National legal framework of protection”. Additionally, the material gathered included reports by national and international organizations and NGOs, as well as European national official documents and academic literature.

The main section of this report, “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions”, was analysed by drawing from the empirical material gathered during the implemented research. Specifically, field qualitative research was conducted in the island of Lesbos and Athens from June 2018 to December 2018 at a meso and micro level. We also conducted short discussions with actors of the meso level more recently, during the writing of this report, in order to update our data regarding some of the recent relevant developments.

The meso level included 15 semi-structured interviews with executives and employees of the authorities, international organisations and NGOs. Additionally, a round-table discussion organised by the University of the Aegean working group in November 2018 provided crucial insights to the research. Field research faced some limitations regarding the meso level interviews: The great interest shown in migration and refugee issues and the arrival of many researchers to Lesbos, especially after 2015, seems to have tired those involved in dealing with the subject. Some informants were initially cautious and did not want to talk about these matters due to the link of the research with the European Commission. Another problem is that Lesbos is a small place, and everyone knows each other; as a consequence, the identity of the participant is instantly recognised. It is for this reason that some of the interviewees from the meso level spoke as individuals and not on behalf of the organisations they work for. These difficulties were mainly overcome by virtue of the familiarisation of researchers with people working in organisations, which helped them gain their trust. That said, there were others who did want to talk of or report the problems they face in the field. The questions regarding issues of refugee protection addressed to interviewees from the meso level during the semi-structured interviews are presented in Table 1 below.

As for the micro level, 34 semi-structured interviews were conducted with refugees living in Moria Camp and in Athens, including a focus-group interview. The sample was approached using the snowball method. The interviewees were aware of the aims of this research and their anonymity and desire to speak off the record at certain moments of the interview were respected. Twelve (12) interviewees were of Afghan origin, of which 8 were raised in other countries such as Iran or Pakistan. Eight (8) came from Syria, including 3 Kurds. Additionally, there was a wide range of interviewees from other countries of origin such as Burundi (2 interviewees), Iraq (2 interviewees), Somalia (2 interviewees), Iran, Palestine, Cameroon, Congo, Eritrea, Guinea and Sudan. The proportion of men and women interviewees were: 75.75% males (25 in absolute numbers), 9.10% women (3 in absolute numbers), 15.15%

couples (5 in absolute numbers) and 1 group interview (with both men and a woman). Most interviewees were aged 18 to 37, with some exceptions of older individuals. The questions regarding issues of refugee protection addressed to interviewees from the micro level during the semi-structured interviews are presented in Table 2 below. The list of the micro level interviewees with pseudonyms and personal information is provided in the Table 6 in Appendices.

The qualitative analysis of the interview material was conducted using NVivo software and organised on the basis of the major research issues of RESPOND (such as borders, protection, reception and integration). The NVivo material regarding protection was specifically used for the needs of this report. Despite the usefulness of NVivo for the analysis of large numbers of interviews, it should be mentioned that in some cases the use of this kind of software has specific limitations. For example, in the present case, the exported nodes sometimes removed the personal history of interviewees. Thus, in some cases, it was necessary to reincorporate information from the interviews' transcriptions – and not only from the nodes exported through NVivo – in order to take into account, the specific context of the interviewee's experiences, perceptions and practices.

Finally, as we have already mentioned, this report was written in a differentiated political context in Greece than the previous ones, due to the recent national elections in Greece and the veer to conservatism. As a result, and considering announcements made by the government, we can expect significant changes regarding refugee protection and asylum procedures. These developments highlight and corroborate the overall temporary and fluid character of the investigated issues, a methodological concern that should be mentioned.

Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework

Important Developments since 2011

During the 1990s, since the so-called transformation of Greece from an emigration to a destination country, immigration and asylum policies in Greece were characterised by the adoption of strict immigration laws, deportation policies and a negative coverage of the migration phenomenon by the media and political discourse. At the same time, as a Member State of the European Union (EU) since 1981, Greece has participated in the attempts to gradually harmonise migration and asylum policies, which began with the Maastricht Treaty and continued and became stronger with Greece's signature of the Schengen Agreement in 1992. As for the Greek legal system on asylum, it is based on the 1951 Geneva Convention and its 1967 Protocol, as well as on EU legislation on the Common European Asylum System (CEAS). Greece is bound to provide asylum to those who meet the criteria and is also obliged to respect the binding Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, which recognises the right to asylum (Petracou et al., 2018).

During the 1990-2005 period, the main focus was on combatting irregular arrivals, exercising border controls, as well as registering the migrant population and giving them temporary residence and employment permits. At the same time, especially in the 2000s, asylum policies were very restrictive: they consisted of detention, time-consuming procedures and very low rates of recognition and granted mainly temporary humanitarian protection (Ibid.).

A significant development in asylum procedures in Greece took place in 2011, when the Hellenic Parliament passed Law 3907/2011 for the “establishment of an Asylum Service and a First Reception Service, the adaptation of the Greek legislation to the provisions of Directive 2008/115/EC ‘with regard to the common rules and procedures in Member States for the return of illegally staying third-country nationals’ and other provisions”.

In spring 2015, during the deep recession which caused economic and social hardship in Greece and as a result of the war (mainly in Syria) and of the overall adverse conditions prevailing in other countries, refugees mostly from Syria but also from Iraq, Afghanistan, Eritrea and Somalia started to enter Greece in larger numbers. Most refugees entered Greece by boat from Turkey to the Greek islands Lesbos, Chios, Kos and Samos. In 2015 alone, more than 850,000 migrants made the crossing to Greece in an attempt to make their way to other EU countries.

Following the closure of the so-called Western Balkans Corridor and the EU–Turkey Statement of 18 March 2016, Hellenic Parliament adopted Law 4375/2016. This law introduced a considerable number of changes regarding the legal framework, first reception and asylum procedures and the management of refugee flows and led to a greater involvement of European Asylum Support Office (EASO) and European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) in Greece. Most notably, it introduced an “exceptional” “Fast-Track Border” Asylum Procedure, the blanket detention of migrants

in closed “Reception and Identification Centres” (RICs) and the application of the concept of “safe third country” so as to provide a basis for the return to Turkey of arrivals after March 20th 2016, as foreseen by the EU-Turkey Statement (Karamanidou, 2017). Law 4375/2016 also established the new Ministry for Migration Policy, with responsibilities relating to immigration and integration, along with the independent Asylum Service operating under the ministry’s supervision.

Asylum applications in Greece increased significantly due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands where Hotspots are established and where crucial protection issues are on a steady rise. The Hotspot approach is still being implemented on the Eastern Aegean islands, as developed by the European Commission in order to manage the so-called “refugee crisis and assist frontline Member States facing disproportionate migratory pressure at their external borders” (European Parliament, 2018). The provision of operational support under the Hotspot approach would focus on registration and identification procedures, return operations and on assisting in the implementation of the temporary relocation schemes by redefining the Hotspots in Greece as closed (or “secure”) facilities.

Another significant development regarding the legal framework is the recent Law 4540/2018 that amended Law 4375/2016. Law 4540/2018 upgrades the role of the EASO and expands its operation from assessing vulnerability, conducting interviews and drafting opinions in border procedures to similar competencies in the regular asylum procedure.

At the political level, the SYRIZA-led coalition government of 2015-2019 has been replaced by the right-wing ND government following the recent national elections of July 2019. The Ministry of Migration Policy, established in 2016, has been abolished as an independent ministry and transformed into a General Secretariat for Immigration Policy, Reception and Asylum belonging to the Ministry of Citizen Protection and headed by an Alternate Minister of Citizen Protection “responsible for Migration Policy”. Additionally, a wide range of conservative measures on refugee issues have been – mostly – announced but also implemented. Examples of measures already taken include sweep operations in refugee squats in the centre of Athens and the transfer of refugees to camps located in remote mainland areas. Some of the announcements and future plans refer to the stricter securitisation of the Greek borders, the conversion of the camps to “closed centres”, etc.

National legal and institutional framework regarding “asylum procedure and refugee protection”

As mentioned, the Greek legal system on asylum is based on the 1951 Geneva Convention and its 1967 Protocol, as well as on the EU legislation on the Common European Asylum System (CEAS). Greece is bound to provide asylum to those who meet the criteria and is also obliged to respect the binding Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, which recognises the right to asylum. The relevant articles of the Greek Constitution are the following:

The Constitution provides for “respect and protection of the value of the human being” (art. 2); “full protection of their life, honour and liberty irrespective of nationality, race or language and of religious or political beliefs” for all persons living within Greek territory (art. 5, par. 2) and inviolability of personal liberty (art. 5, para. 3). Furthermore, “no person shall be arrested or imprisoned without a reasoned judicial warrant which must be served at the moment of arrest or detention pending trial, except when caught in the act of committing a crime” (art. 6, par. 1) and “torture, any bodily maltreatment, impairment of health or the use of psychological violence, as well as any other offence against human dignity are prohibited and punished as provided by law” (art. 7, par. 2). “Every person shall be entitled to receive legal protection by the courts and may plead before them his views concerning his rights or interests, as specified by law” (art. 20, par. 1) and “the right of a person to a prior hearing also applies in any administrative action or measure adopted at the expense of his rights or interests” (art. 20, par. 2).

More specifically, the term “protection” is used in line with the way in which it is defined by the current Qualification Directive 2011/95/EU “on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection and for the content of the protection granted (recast) (Council Directive 2011/95/EU), that amends Council Directive 2004/83/EC of the 29th of April 2004. The Qualification Directive sets out criteria for applicants to qualify for refugee status or subsidiary protection and foresees a series of rights for its beneficiaries (residence permits, travel documents, access to employment and education, social welfare and healthcare). In Greece, the Qualification Directive was transposed into Greek legislation through Presidential Decree 141/21-10-2013.

Additionally, the Asylum Procedures Directive 2013/32/EU of the 26th of June 2013 “on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection” (Council Directive 2013/32/EU) establishes common standards of safeguards and guarantees to access a fair and efficient asylum procedure. The Asylum Procedures Directive was transposed into Greek legislation through Law 4375/2016. Furthermore, the Temporary Protection Directive 2001/55/EC sets minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof (Council Directive 2011/55/EC).

Asylum procedures

The asylum procedures in Greek legislation are currently defined through Law 4375/2016 and its later amendments. According to Law 4375/2016 (art. 36), any alien or stateless person has the right to apply for international protection. Additionally, article 39 points out that all applications for international protection are initially examined regarding the recognition of refugee status and, in case these are not fulfilled, they are examined for the recognition of subsidiary protection status. Additionally, according to Presidential Decree 113/2013, every foreigner or stateless person has the right to submit an application for international protection, provided that he or she meets the criteria of the Geneva Convention and applicable national law or qualifies for subsidiary protection. The competent national authorities of first reception are obliged to inform the applicants of such rights. Decisions are made by the Asylum Service on a case-by-case basis; the review is required to be an objective, unbiased, and non-discriminatory review of the facts (Papademetriou, 2016).

The main procedures that could take place according to the Greek legal framework are the following¹:

First instance procedure:

Asylum applications are submitted before the Asylum Service. Twelve Regional Asylum Offices and eleven Asylum Units were operational at the end of 2018. The Asylum Service is also competent for applying the Dublin procedure, with most requests and transfers concerning family reunification in other Member States.

The interview is one of the most crucial parts of the asylum procedure. The applicant should be provided with all the necessary information regarding the procedure. If the applicant is not able to communicate with the interviewer due to a language barrier, an interpreter must be available. A lawyer representing the applicant can also attend the interview. The interview is confidential and can be audio recorded. After the interview, the decision whether to grant the applicant refugee status, subsidiary protection status or reject the application is provided (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 32).

In April 2016, the possibility for the Asylum Service to be assisted by EASO personnel “exceptionally” and “in cases where third-country nationals or stateless persons arrive in large numbers” within the framework of the Fast-Track Border Procedure was introduced. By a subsequent amendment in June 2016, national legislation explicitly provided the possibility for the asylum interview within the Fast-Track Border Procedure to be conducted by an EASO caseworker. According to Law 4540/2018, the possibility of participation of Greek-speaking EASO personnel in the regular procedure on the mainland was also introduced. The law provides that, in case of urgent need, EASO personnel can carry out any administrative procedures needed for processing applications. In fact, EASO caseworkers have been conducting interviews under the regular procedure in Greece since September 2018.

¹ For a more thorough presentation, see also (Petracou et al., 2018)

- Regular procedure: Applicants are subject to personal interviews through interpretation by staff who must have experience in such matters and who are expected to maintain confidentiality. Before June 2013, the authority responsible for receiving and examining applications was the Hellenic Police. Since June 2013, the designated authority for examining international protection applications in the first instance under the regular or accelerated procedure is the Asylum Service, including its central offices in Athens and Regional Asylum Offices (RAO) across the country.
- Accelerated procedure: Law 4375/2016, art. 51(6) provides that an application may be registered and examined by way of priority for persons who: a) belong to vulnerable groups or are in need of special procedural guarantees, b) apply from detention, at the border or from a Reception and Identification Centre, c) are likely to fall within the Dublin procedure, d) have cases reasonably believed to be well-founded, e) have cases which may be considered as manifestly unfounded, f) represent a threat to national security or public order or g) file a Subsequent Application (AIDA, 2019a, pp. 43-44).
- Fast-Track Border Procedure: According to Law 4375/2016 (art. 63 and 65) the Fast-track Border Procedure refers to applicants subject to the EU-Turkey Statement (applicants arriving to the North-eastern Aegean islands after the 20th of March 2016) and takes place in the Reception and Identification Centres (RIC) where Hotspots are established and before the RAO of Rhodes. Vulnerable people and applicants for family reunification are exempted from this procedure, as they should follow the regular procedure. Until August 2017, requests by vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification were referred to a Regional Asylum Office (RAO) on the mainland and, as a result, the geographical restriction was lifted for their cases. Since then and due to conditions of overcrowding in mainland RAOs, the guidelines of the Asylum Service have changed, and applications regarding the regular procedure (such as those of vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification) are also examined on the islands. Based on the relevant law, the geographical restriction is lifted only for those who have a positive decision to their application and for some cases of vulnerable applicants only after Ministerial Decisions regarding the decongestion of the islands. Under the Fast-Track Border Procedure, inter alia, interviews may also be conducted by EASO staff, while very short deadlines are provided to applicants. The concept of “safe third country” has been applied for the first time for applicants belonging to nationalities with a recognition rate of over 25%, including Syrians (AIDA, 2019a, p. 26).
- Procedure for the application of the EC Dublin III Regulation: Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of the 26th of June 2013, also referred to as the ‘Dublin III’ Regulation, as well as its two Implementing Regulations, provide the legal framework for determining the EU Member State responsible for examining the application for international protection lodged in another Member State by a third-country national or stateless person. Regarding the outgoing procedure from first reception countries such as Greece, on the basis of the Dublin III Regulation applicants

have the right to request family reunification with a family member or relative who is present in another EU Member State-party to 'Dublin III', under specific circumstances (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 31)².

Subsequent application:

Subsequent application is an application for international protection which is submitted once more after a final negative decision by the Hellenic Police or the Asylum Service concerning the prior application has been issued. In order to submit a subsequent application to the Asylum Service, applicants should have been notified by the Hellenic Police or the Asylum Service with a final negative decision which they have appealed against before the administrative courts; or nine months should have elapsed since a decision to discontinue the examination of the application has been issued; or nine months should have elapsed since they have expressly withdrawn their application and furthermore they have new reasons for applying for international protection (Asylum Service, 2019). The subsequent application also refers to persons who may have entered Greece irregularly, through sea or land borders, without being registered or detained or arrested before arriving to Athens.

The subsequent application should be submitted to one of the Regional Asylum Offices or Asylum Units and the applicant must submit in writing the new important elements that have emerged. After submitting the subsequent application, applicants are not provided with an asylum applicant's card. The Asylum Service will examine the new elements and decide whether they are of importance regarding the application for international protection. Only if the subsequent application is considered as admissible the examination of the application will continue and the applicant will be provided with an asylum applicant's card. If the Asylum Service rejects the subsequent application, the applicant may submit an appeal before the Appeals Authority (Asylum Service, 2019).

Second instance procedures / Appeal:

The authorities responsible for examining appeals before June 2013 were the Appeal Committees, comprised of a civil servant from the Ministry of the Interior or from the Ministry of Justice, a representative of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and a lawyer specialising in refugee as well as human rights law. Since 2013, appeals are examined by the Appeals Authority, first established by Law 3907/2011. Moreover, Law 4375/2016 (amended by Law 4399/2016) establishes the Appeals Authority as an autonomous service which reports directly to the Ministry of Migration Policy. An appeal must be lodged within 30 days in the regular procedure, 15 days in the accelerated procedure, in case of an inadmissibility decision or where the applicant is detained, and 5 days in the border procedure and Fast-Track Border

² In September 2015, the European Council adopted the Council Decisions (EU) 2015/1523 and 2015/1601 establishing a temporary "Emergency Relocation Scheme", for the relocation of a total of 160,000 newly arrived asylum seekers from Greece and Italy to other EU Member States, as an emergency measure to alleviate pressure on the two countries. The relocation scheme constituted a partial derogation from the Dublin Regulation criteria. Out of the target of 66,400 asylum seekers to be relocated from Greece, 22,822 had effectively been transferred by the end of the scheme (Aida, 2019a, p. 61). In accordance with the Council Decisions, the relocation scheme was officially ceased at the end of September 2017 but the Relocation Unit continued operations on pending cases until the end of 2017.

Procedure. The appeal has automatic suspensive effect. The procedure before the Appeals Committee shall be generally in writing, and the examination of the appeals shall be performed based on the elements from the case file, without the presence of the appellant. During the examination procedure of the appeal, the Committee shall examine both the legality of the act under appeal and the merits of the case and shall accept or reject the appeal and issue a relevant decision (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 33). A further reform in March 2017 foresees the involvement of rapporteurs appointed by EASO to assist the Appeals Committees in the examination of appeals (AIDA, 2019a, p. 26).

Judicial review:

Applicants for international protection may lodge an application for annulment (*αίτηση ακύρωσης*) of a second instance decision before the Administrative Court of Appeals within 60 days from the notification of the decision. Following the application for annulment, an application for suspension (*αίτηση αναστολής*) can be filed. Persons whose asylum application is rejected at second instance no longer have “asylum-seeker” status. Before the amendments introduced by Law 4540/2018, national legislation provided that, following the lodging of the application for annulment, an application for suspension and a request for interim order (*προσωρινή διαταγή*) could be filed. The interim order was to be issued within a few days and the application for suspension was usually scheduled for a later date. Following Law 4540/2018, echoing the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement and pressure to limit the appeal stages, the stages of interim order and application for suspension have been merged into one. The decision on this single application for temporary protection from removal should be issued within 15 days from the lodging of the application. The application for annulment and application for suspension do not have an automatic suspensive effect. Therefore, between the application of suspension and the decision of the court, there is no guarantee that the applicant will not be removed for the territory (Ibid., pp. 81-82).

For an overview of the Asylum Procedures in the context of the EU-Turkey Statement, see Figure 1 in Appendix. Additionally, for an overview of the legal framework see Tables 4 and 5 in Appendix.

The criteria for recognition and the rights of refugees, those eligible for subsidiary protection and applicants for international protection

Refugee status: A refugee is defined in accordance with the definition provided in article 1A of the Geneva Convention as a person who “owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to return to it”. Refugee status is granted to a third-country national or a stateless person who meets the criteria established by Presidential Decree 141/2013. Legal assistance

is essential to guarantee the procedural guarantees of detainees. Regarding the criteria for the granting of refugee status, see Petracou et al. (2018, p. 47).

Subsidiary protection status: In order for an applicant to be granted subsidiary protection status there must be substantial grounds to believe that this person, who does not otherwise qualify for refugee status, would face a real risk of suffering serious harm if returned to his/her country of origin. The qualification for subsidiary protection from a “real risk of suffering serious harm” includes the death penalty or execution, torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, or a serious and individualised threat to persons due to violence in the case of internal armed conflict (Ibid.). Prior to Law 4375/2016, the rights of international protection beneficiaries in Greece (recognised refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection) were regulated by Presidential Decree 141/2013, which incorporated Directive 95/2011/EC on the procedures of determining the refugee status. For both persons granted refugee status and those granted subsidiary protection, Greek law foresees the following rights: a) family unity, b) residence permit, c) travel documents/repatriation, d) education, e) access to employment, f) health care (for more details, see Petracou et al., 2018, pp. 49-51).

Applicants for international protection: According to Greek Law 4251/2014, a beneficiary of international protection is a foreign national or stateless person to whom the competent Greek authority has granted refugee or beneficiary of subsidiary protection status. A person seeking international protection is any alien or stateless person who declares to any Greek authority, orally or in writing, that he/she is seeking asylum or requests not to be deported because he/she is in fear of persecution because of his/her race, religion, nationality, participation in a particular social group or his/her political beliefs, or because he/she is in danger of suffering serious harm in his/her country of origin or country of previous residence, especially because he/she is in danger of facing the death penalty or execution, torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or his/her life or physical integrity is in danger because of an international or civil war. Also, any alien who is transferred to Greece from a European state implementing the EC “Dublin III” Regulation is regarded as a person seeking international protection (Ibid., p. 48). As of June 2013, applications for international protection fall within a new procedure established by Presidential Decree 113/2013. Every foreigner or stateless person has the right to apply for international protection, provided that he or she meets the criteria of the Geneva Convention and applicable national law or qualifies for subsidiary protection. The competent first reception national authorities are obliged to inform the applicants of such rights. Decisions are made by the Asylum Service on a case-by-case basis (Ibid.).

The rights of applicants for international protection include the following: a) Deportation is prohibited until the examination of the application is completed, b) He/she may move freely throughout the country, apart from specific areas of the country, c) If the applicant is homeless, he/she may ask to be hosted in a Reception Centre or another facility, while provision of accommodation will depend on the availability of spaces, d) The applicant has the right to work under the conditions set by Greek law, e) The applicant has the right to receive medical and pharmaceutical treatment free of charge, provided that he/she is uninsured and indigent, and f) As long as the applicant remains an applicant for international protection, he/she cannot travel

outside Greece and cannot transfer his/her family from their country of origin to Greece (Ibid., pp. 48-49). Regarding the obligations of the applicant for international protection, he/she should remain in Greece until the examination of the application is completed, among others (For more details, see Petracou et al., 2018, p. 49).

Additionally, Greece is obliged under the EU Reception Conditions Directive to provide an adequate standard of living for applicants which will guarantee their subsistence and protect their physical and mental health (Article 17), to provide emergency care and essential treatment of illnesses and of serious mental disorders and to provide necessary medical assistance to applicants with special reception needs, including mental health care (Article 19). This is reflected in the corollary implementing provisions under Greek Law 4375/2016 (Articles 14(5) and 27(2)(b)(cc)) and Greek Law 4540/2018 (Articles 10, 17, 20 and 23).

Reception and Identification Centres and the geographical restriction on the North-eastern Aegean islands

The Greek reception system established by Law 3907/2011 was transformed in April 2015 by what the EU Commission established as the “Hotspot Approach”. In particular, the “Hotspot Approach” was first introduced in the European Agenda on Migration as an initial response to the exceptional flows and is implemented in Greece through the legal framework governing the reception and identification procedure under Law 4375/2016. According to Law 4375/2016, newly arrived persons on the Greek islands should be directly transferred to a Reception and Identification Centre, where they are subject to a 3-day “restriction of freedom of movement within the premises of the centre”, which can be further extended for a maximum of 25 days if reception and identification procedures have not been completed.

As provided by Law 4375/2016 (art. 9, par. 1): “All third-country nationals and stateless persons who enter without complying with the legal formalities in the country shall be submitted to reception and identification procedures” that include:

- the registration of their personal data and the taking and registering of fingerprints for those who have reached the age of 14,
- the verification of their identity and nationality,
- their medical screening and the provision of any necessary care and psychosocial support,
- informing them of their rights and obligations, in particular of the procedure for international protection or the procedure for entering a voluntary return program,
- attention for those belonging to vulnerable groups, so that they can be placed under the appropriate, in each case, procedure and receive specialised care and protection,
- referring those who wish to apply for international protection so that they can start the procedure for such an application,
- referring those who do not apply for international protection or whose application is rejected while they remain in the RIC to the competent authorities

for readmission, removal or return procedures (Petracou et al., 2018, pp. 42-43).

After this period, newly arrived third-country nationals are subject to “geographical restriction” as they are under an obligation not to leave the island and to reside in the Hotspot facilities, in order to undergo the Fast-Track Border Procedure to determine whether Turkey is a “safe third country” for them. The geographical restriction is lifted in the following cases:

- all applicants receiving international protection have their restriction lifted immediately,
- all Syrian applicants whose claim has been determined as admissible due to the inapplicability of the safe third country concept have their restriction lifted immediately,
- all applicants exempted due to the applicability of the Dublin Regulation have their restriction lifted immediately,
- following a change in practice in May 2017, Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability have their restriction lifted immediately, while non-Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability do not have their restriction lifted until they undergo the personal interview” (AIDA, 2018, p.121). This change in administrative practices as of May 2017 regarding the lifting of the geographical restriction for vulnerable non-Syrian applicants has further exacerbated overcrowding on the islands (AIDA, 2018, p. 121).

Additionally, it should be mentioned that geographical restriction is largely linked to the Fast-Track Border Procedure referred to previously; for those examined under this procedure the geographical restriction is maintained. Vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification are exempted from the Fast-Track Border Procedure, as they should follow the regular procedure. Until August 2017, requests by vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification were referred to a Regional Asylum Office (RAO) of the mainland and, as a result, the geographical restriction was lifted for their cases. Since then and due to conditions of overcrowding in mainland RAOs, the guidelines of the Asylum Service have changed and applications regarding the regular procedure (such as those of vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification) are also examined on the islands. Thus, the geographical restriction is lifted only after Ministerial Decisions regarding the decongestion of the islands and only for those having a positive decision on their application or certain cases of vulnerable persons.

People arriving through the Evros border and not through the Aegean islands are not subject to the EU-Turkey Statement. Therefore, they are not subject to the Fast-Track Border Procedure, their claims are not examined under the safe third country concept, and there is no geographical restriction imposed upon them (AIDA, 2019a, p. 37).

Five ‘Hotspots’ operate under the legal form of Reception and Identification Centres (RICs) in Greece, in the main islands of reception: Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Kos and Leros. In the beginning, Hotspots in Greece operated as open facilities to register, screen and assist arriving migrants and asylum-seekers before their swift transfer to

the Greek mainland. Immediately after the launch of the EU-Turkey Statement on 18 March 2016, Reception and Identification Centres turned into closed (or “secure”) facilities. After the implementation of the geographical restriction on the North-eastern Aegean islands (following the EU-Turkey Statement), the numbers of refugees remaining in Moria Hotspot have significantly increased.

A wide range of official actors are present in the RICs:

- Police: The Police are responsible for guarding the external area of the Hotspot facilities, as well as for the identification and verification of the nationalities of newcomers.
- Frontex: Frontex staff are also engaged in nationality identification and verification. Although Frontex should have an assisting role, they are practically the only ones conducting nationality screenings, as the Greek authorities lack relevant capacity and certain resources such as interpreters. The carrying out of said procedures by Frontex is defined by an internal regulation. It should be noted that, even though the Greek authorities may base their decision concerning the nationality of a newcomer exclusively on a Frontex assessment, documents issued by the latter are considered to be a ‘non-paper’ and are thereby inaccessible to individuals. This renders the dispute of Frontex findings extremely difficult in practice.
- UNHCR / IOM: Information is provided by UNHCR and International Organisation for Migration (IOM) staff.
- Asylum Service: The Asylum Service is also present in the Hotspots. According to Law 4375/2016, those registered by the RIS expressing their will to seek international protection shall be referred to the competent Regional Asylum Office in order to have their claims registered and processed.
- EASO: EASO is also engaged in the asylum procedure. EASO experts have a rather active role within the scope of the Fast-Track Border Procedure, as they conduct first-instance personal interviews, they issue opinions regarding asylum applications and they are also involved in the vulnerability assessment procedure. Following a legislative reform in 2018, Greek-speaking EASO personnel can also conduct any administrative action for processing asylum applications, including in the regular procedure.
- RIS: The RIS outsourced medical and psychosocial care provision to NGOs until mid-2017. Since then, the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (*Κέντρο Ελέγχου και Πρόληψης Νοσημάτων*, KEELPNO), a private law entity supervised and funded directly by the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity, has been gradually taking over the provision of medical and psychosocial services. Serious shortcomings have been noted in 2018 due to the insufficient number of medical staff in the RIC (see also Identification) (Petraçou et al., 2018, pp. 43-44)

Registration

Part III of Law 4375/2016, as modified by Law 4399/2016 and Law 4540/2018, transposes the provisions of Article 6 the recast Asylum Procedures Directive relating to access to the procedure. As outlined below, Greek law uses the term “simple

registration” (*απλή καταγραφή*) to describe the notion of “registration”, and “full registration” (*πλήρης καταγραφή*) to describe the notion of “lodging” an application under the Directive.

The Registration of applications (before the competent receiving authorities, i.e. the Regional Asylum Offices (RAO), the Asylum Units (AAU), Mobile Asylum Units of the Asylum Service or EASO), should be immediately followed by the “full registration” (*πλήρης καταγραφή*) of the application. After the “full registration” of the asylum application by the Asylum Service, an application is considered lodged (*κατατεθειμένη*). However, when full registration is not possible “for whatever reason”, following a decision of the Director of the Asylum Service, the Asylum Service may conduct a “basic registration” (*απλή καταγραφή*) of the asylum seeker’s necessary details within 3 working days and then proceed to the full registration as soon as possible and by way of priority. The time limits for the basic registration of the application may be extended to 10 working days in cases where many applications are submitted simultaneously and render the registration particularly difficult (AIDA, 2019a, pp. 38-39).

Regarding the lodging of applications, no time limit is set by law except as referenced by Law 4375/2016, which requires all applicants to appear before the competent authorities in person, without delay, in order to submit their application for international protection. According to the latest decision of the Director of the Asylum Service issued in January 2018, the “asylum-seeker card”, which is provided to all persons who have fully registered their application, is valid for 6 months. However, asylum-seeker cards given to applicants who reside on the islands of Lesbos, Samos, Chios, Leros, Kos and Rhodes and are subject to a “geographical limitation” are valid for 1 month (AIDA, 2019a).

Detention

According to Law 3907/2011 art. 7, third-country nationals who enter Greece without residence status or documentation are subject to administrative detention. The purpose of this policy is to identify individuals, manage removals—as well as encourage voluntary returns—and deter further arrivals. When detention is imposed, it is done without a proper individual assessment or consideration of alternatives to detention. Particularly concerning is the absence of a proper judicial review, as well as the prolongation of the detention for periods that can exceed the maximum 18-month timeframe allowed by the Returns Directive.

In line with the European legal framework, both Law 4375/2016 as well as Presidential Decree 114/2010 underline that “the detention of applicants for international protection shall be imposed for the minimum necessary period. Delays in administrative procedures that cannot be attributed to the applicant shall not justify a continuation of detention”. Nevertheless, a person who applies for international protection while in detention is likely to remain there for a very long time: Pursuant to Law 4375/2016, Greek authorities retain the right to detain an asylum-seeker based on one of the following grounds: a) to determine his or her identity or nationality, b) when there is a risk of absconding, c) when it is highly probable that the application for international protection has the sole purpose of delaying the enforcement of a return

decision, d) for reasons of national security or public order. The exact same grounds figure among the provisions of Presidential Decree 114/2010. The only difference is that Presidential Decree 114/2010 also adds that an asylum seeker can be detained if deemed necessary “for the prompt and effective” completion of the application for asylum.

According to Law 4375/2016, detained asylum-seekers and third-country nationals under removal procedures are kept in pre-removal detention centres established in accordance with the provisions of the Returns Directive. In cases of detention of applicants, the competent authorities shall apply the following as per case: a) ensure that women are detained in a separate area than men and guarantee due respect for the privacy of families in detention, b) avoid detaining women during pregnancy and for 3 months after giving birth, c) provide appropriate medical care to detainees, d) ensure the right of detainees to legal representation, e) ensure that detainees are informed in a language they understand of the reasons and the duration of their detention, their right and means to challenge the detention decision and their right to free legal assistance (Law 4375/2016, art. 46).

Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions

This section focuses on the practices, experiences and perceptions regarding asylum procedures and refugee protection, drawing from the material gathered during the implemented qualitative research and, more specifically, the meso and micro level semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and refugees respectively. More specifically, in this section we focus on the implementation of refugee protection by highlighting processes of access to asylum procedures, experiences of registration procedures, experiences with actors and legal aid, information and consulting. We also reflect on the recent changes that have affected the asylum procedures in Greece, such as the establishment of the Hotspot regime and the EU-Turkey Statement. We focus on gaps emerging between laws/policies and their implementation, examine the institutions and social actors involved in the implementation of international protection, provide insights regarding vulnerability issues and refugee categorisation and analyse living conditions in the Hotspots as a factor affecting protection issues. Additionally, special attention is given to dimensions of gender dynamics and vulnerable groups. Our analysis is based on extracts from the meso and micro level semi-structured interviews, combined with sources such as reports from actors and institutions.

As already mentioned in the Introduction of this report, due to recent changes in the Greek political landscape after the 2019 national elections, issues of asylum procedures and refugee protection remain fluid today, as a series of relevant changes have been announced but not yet legislated. Additionally, following the recent European elections, the UNHCR has called on the newly-elected Greek members of the European Parliament to adopt seven key proposals to strengthen the protection of refugees at both the national and EU level (European Commission, 2019).

Access to the Asylum Procedure for newly arrived persons

Newly arrived individuals seeking international protection can register with either:

- The RAO of Northern Evros, having been referred by the First Reception Centre (FRC) in Fylakio (Evros),
- The RAO of Southern Evros (*Alexandroupoli*),
- The RAO of Lesbos, following referral by the First Reception Mobile Unit or police on the island of Lesbos,
- The RAO of Rhodes, following referral by police on the Dodecanese islands, or
- The RAO of Attica.

Evros Region: New arrivals at the land border with Turkey wishing to seek international protection are referred by the First Reception Centre (FRC) in Fylakio (Evros) to the RAO of Northern Evros. However, the formal registration of their application often happens after they have been transferred from the FRC to the adjacent pre-removal centre (UNHCR, 2014, p. 16).

North-eastern Aegean Sea: New arrivals at the islands of the north-eastern Aegean Sea are referred by the First Reception Mobile Unit or police on the island of Lesbos to the RAO of Lesbos which operates within the “identification centre” run by the police. This RAO also covers Chios through teleconferencing; however, so far only four applications for international protection have been filed from there, in 2014. Lesbos RAO does not deal with applications for international protection lodged in Samos. Those who apply for international protection in Samos are transferred as detainees to Athens for the registration of their application. As the process encounters practical difficulties, and transfer entails delays, practically no applications for international protection were submitted in Samos, even though Samos has received a significant number of arrivals since 2014 (UNHCR, 2014, p. 16).

South-eastern Aegean Sea: New arrivals at the islands of the South-eastern Aegean Sea who want to seek international protection can do so with the police, after which they are transferred to the island of Rhodes and remain in detention at least until the Asylum Service issues a recommendation on whether the detention period should be extended or the person should be released. In practice, the number of applications by new arrivals registered by the RAO of Rhodes is very low. As the large majority of new arrivals in the Dodecanese islands in 2014 were Syrians (91,5%), they were released with an order for a 6-month suspension of deportation. Other nationalities did not receive such a suspension of deportation but, instead, were handed a 7 to 30-day notice to leave the country (Ibid.). Another factor contributing to the low number of applications for international protection in these areas is the fact that many individuals prefer to present themselves to the Athens RAO instead. This concerns mainly persons who, as per current practices, are released from detention in the border regions because they originate from countries to which no returns take place, like Syria, Somalia and Eritrea, or because they are families or otherwise considered vulnerable (Ibid.). Resource constraints leading to delays and, thus, to prolonged detention periods also discourage asylum-seekers from applying in these areas of Greece.

Living Conditions at Moria Hotspot

As already mentioned, Greece is obliged under the EU Reception Conditions Directive to provide an adequate standard of living for applicants which will guarantee their subsistence and protect their physical and mental health (Article 17), provide emergency care and essential treatment of illnesses and of serious mental disorders, and provide necessary medical assistance to applicants with special reception needs, including mental health care (Article 19). This is reflected in the corollary implementing provisions under Greek Law 4375/2016 [Articles 14(5) and 27(2)(b)(cc)] and Greek Law 4540/2018 (Articles 10, 17, 20 and 23).

After the implementation of the geographical restriction on the North-eastern Aegean islands (following the EU-Turkey Statement), the numbers of refugees remaining in Moria Hotspot in Lesbos island significantly increased. As a result, Moria Hotspot constitutes to date not only a Reception and Identification Centre (where the first registration of refugees takes place) but also a place where refugees remain for a long period of time. Considering refugee protection not merely as institutional protection, in accordance to the relevant laws, but also as the provision of full and

equal respect for their human rights and coverage of their basic human needs, survival and physical security, we approach the Hotspot system as a regime that is highly related to protection issues.

Drawing from the field research conducted, reception and living conditions raise serious concerns regarding the protection of refugees, as their basic needs and human rights are threatened and violated every day. It is, therefore, important to highlight aspects of living conditions in Moria Hotspot as they emerge from both the interviews conducted and the large numbers of reports from actors or the press: As our interviewees mention: “And you arrived to Moria? Yes, we arrived to a big jail (Michael), and “let's talk about Moria. Moria is a bad place. You can go there, and you'll see. There aren't many things to say about Moria. [...] There are no words to talk about Moria” (Jack).

The first concern is the overcrowding that prevails in Moria: despite the fact that the site has an official capacity of approximately 3,100, it is currently home to some 13,000 (as of September 2019). This has gradually led to the creation of an informal camp in the surrounding olive grove known as “The Jungle”. In this area, refugees live in unheated tents, on mattresses or blankets on the ground, without adequate infrastructures. Both inside Moria Hotspot and in the neighbouring olive grove, the facilities provided are insufficient for the large numbers of people. For example, it has been reported that washing and hygiene facilities are very limited, there is limited access to running water, and there is no hot water in the bathrooms and no electricity in the olive grove. Considering also the lack of cleanliness, especially in the olive grove, the overall conditions are unsanitary. Narratives also report insufficient food provision for all: in order to get food on an everyday basis, people have to spend day and night in a queue, a particular burden for the most vulnerable and especially during winter.

Moria is a very big problem. Very, very big problem, because I remained there for six months. There is no warm water, ladies have to take bath with cold water. Now they have separated the bathrooms of the ladies and gents, but when I was there, they were combined. They used combined bathrooms. No cleaning. There are too many germs. I will give an example; one bathroom is being used by 600 people. Especially for females, it was common for women to have vaginal problems. They don't get clothes, etc. Then the new arrivals, one family gets just one blanket. In this cold weather. They have small children. How should they manage in cold? [...] Because I have seen that mother, were six family members and only had one blanket. And they have put this blanket below her baby. So, all the others were in the cold. They were in a tent without any blanket. And in EASO, when we had to change our (not clear) there is too many African men. Actually, I have too many complains about them especially. First of all, they are very, very large, we are really small, and there is no line for women, a separate line, and for men there is no separate line also. [...] And especially for the doctors. There should be some doctors. Health is very important, I think. In Moria, if someone is going to die, no attention of doctor. Go and drink water, go and drink water. And especially during the water line, food line, all the people know what is going on in the food line. Everyday fighting because of the food line. In the morning we get one, like those who live in Moria. They get one cake with one bottle of water. For this line, the people have to go

in line at night at 2 o'clock. [...] Yes, they have to go in line and stay and next morning at 8:30 they give this cake and water. It means that half of their night they will spend it there. For one bottle of water and a cake. One day, when they started distribution they started to fight. Those who have a large height they can take. Those who are smaller, like me, they cannot take anything. I am talking about my friend. She goes to the food line at 2 o'clock, but in the morning she gets nothing. Always she gets nothing. She starts crying that she has nothing here and what should she do. No water, no cake. [...] And the food for like lunch, they have to go at 11 o'clock in the line and wait until 2 o'clock. And for dinner they have to go at 4 o'clock until 7 o'clock at evening. Suppose that I go late, there is nothing for dinner for me. Everything is finished (Fatima).

Living conditions in Moria Hotspot are also inhumane, especially for the most vulnerable groups such as women, unaccompanied children and victims of torture or sexual violence. “Many women have told us that they fear going outdoors after dark because of the risk of violence. In a few extreme cases, women say they have resorted to wearing diapers at night to avoid having to go to the toilet after dark” (Oxfam, 2019, p. 6). Additionally, fights between asylum-seekers of different groups or ethnicities have been reported as common, including the injury of people caused by violent attacks. As interviewees Thanasis and Mah mention: “You are keeping the refugees in Moria and at the summertime an African lady have to give birth in a tent, an Afghan man’s wife and small kid had to die from heart issues inside the camp”.

I was in Moria, trying to understand why there was a woman sleeping outside First Reception, and she told me her child had been taken by someone who tried to rape it, and she couldn’t go back to the place so she slept there. I went to the police and the officer in charge said yes, well, we know that, we know what has happened, it’s not the first time, the first time we have the attempted rape of a child, it wasn’t the first time. And I said OK, so what now, and he said that, because there have been no reports by the parents, we have done nothing (Volunteer in an NGO at Moria Hotspot).

Gender-related experiences regarding living conditions raise even more serious concerns on refugee protection, as there have been reports of serious incidents of gender-based violence, sexual abuse and even rapes inside Moria Hot Spot, despite the fact that they are not usually reported by the victims. As a volunteer in an NGO in Moria Hotspot mentioned during the interview, “Moria produces violence instead of protection, and the system does not undertake the responsibility”.

There are also many cases where the violence emerges here, so vulnerability must be re-examined and also properly substantiated, or there might be a medical issue arising here or being diagnosed here, or cases of rape occurring here, all this requires a process of proper substantiation, because the people will not go themselves, they will not go and say this or that is going on, someone must dedicate time to them, substantiate everything, etc. [...] And the paradox is that, here, instead of people being protected we see people being retraumatized, there are physical and mental health problems that are created or aggravated here, there is rape and violence here and no one undertakes the protection of these people, a protection they truly need. Moria produces violence

and traumatising experiences, and the system will not assume the responsibility (Volunteer in an NGO in Moria Hotspot).

There have been deaths of refugees due to these conditions since 2017, particularly during the days of snow in the winter of 2017 when people tried to keep warm by lighting fires, sometimes inside the tents. As a participant in the roundtable discussion with actors in Moria Hot Spot (organised by the University of the Aegean in November 2018) mentioned: "People have to die again so that we'll take them out of the frozen tents".

The more recent event of another fire in which a woman burned to death in Moria Hotspot, on Sunday 29 September 2019, raises serious concerns. The woman's death was the third in the last two months. An Afghan teenager was killed in a fight in August and a five-year-old boy was run over by a truck while playing in a cardboard box outside the camp in September.

Registration Procedures and the example of Lesbos island

It should be mentioned in advance that the EU-Turkey Statement, followed by Greek Law 4375/2016, constituted a turning point for asylum procedures in Greece. Before the implementation of this framework, newly arrived persons arrested at the Greek borders were provided with a Police Note mentioning they should leave the country within the period of 1 month. This note also provided certification of the date of irregular entry into Greek territory. After receiving this note they were free to move throughout the country and, if arrested by the police after the one-month period, they were kept in detention centres for the purpose of their removal. After the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement and Law 4375/2016, due to the new asylum procedures imposed, asylum applications rose dramatically.

Upon their arrival at Moria Hot Spot, refugees are immediately subject to the registration procedure. Following recent Law 4375/2016 and the EU-Turkey Statement, beginning procedures for the determination of their status is the only option for new arrivals, even if their plans did not include staying in Greece.

-I knew that before, since I was in Turkey, this is a European Country. I don't know, I never realised what was going to happen on the way. They kept me once I arrived, I was told though that I would be free to move, to go wherever I want. In Europe, I thought. But that was not the case now.

-What was the case?

-The case was when you came here first, they ask you two different things. Will you want to claim asylum, or you want to go back to your country? To stay here, you need to claim asylum (Willy).

In general, the problem is, you can come to... When you come to Moria, you are told that you're not going to spend as much time... as you never even realise. What should you do? Normally, they say, you have 25 days to ask for asylum. To ask for asylum, or you have right to leave the country or let them know to which country you really want to go. They ask you if you have any relative in other country. That's the question they ask (Willy).

While people wait for their registration, they are supposed to stay at a big securitized space, the so called “pre-registration tent”, “new arrivals tent” or “quarantine”. This area is of controlled access and no one is allowed to enter except for authorised actors and community leaders. On occasions, this space has been overcrowded and suffocating living conditions have been mentioned by the interviewees. People are usually stacked by the dozens or hundreds in substandard conditions which have a negative impact on their physical or mental health. They are later on transferred to the central area of the Reception and Identification Centre (RIC) for the implementation of the Registration and Identification procedure which, as already mentioned, includes:

- the registration of their personal data and the taking and registering of fingerprints for those who have reached the age of 14,
- the verification of their identity and nationality,
- their medical screening and the provision of any necessary care and psychosocial support,
- informing them of their rights and obligations, in particular of the procedure for international protection or the procedure for entering a voluntary return program,
- attention to those belonging to vulnerable groups so that they be placed under the appropriate, in each case, procedure and receive specialised care and protection,
- the referral of those who wish to apply for international protection so that they begin the relevant procedures,
- the referral of those who will not apply for international protection or whose application has been rejected while they remain in the RIC to the competent authorities for readmission, removal or return procedures (Petraçou et al., 2018, pp. 42-43).

As already mentioned, the police and Frontex are the competent authorities for fingerprinting and taking photos. Specific experiences with these actors relating to this procedure were reported, mainly from women refugees who were forced to have their photo taken without their hijab.

-In Moria, the first day we arrived it was raining. In Moria, EuroRelief (NGO)... At first, they took us for photographs and for fingerprints. All the fingerprints and this part, and they took pictures of our faces without the hijab

-Without?

-Yes without. If I say I will wear it, they say no, you are here... So, I can see your hair also. Yes, they took off the hijab and took pictures...

-Did you ask them not to take it off?

-Yes, but they didn't agree. They said no. Your picture will not be OK then. The system cannot accept you here. So, they took the picture and then they sent us to a large tent in Moria, they were EuroRelief, then they gave us police paper, we show the police paper... (Fatima).

The third problem is Frontex, when we arrived here, we are from Afghanistan [...] they have two Iranian translators here. They either [...] like six months child, they write eight years old, [...] from Afghanistan, they write Iran. So, the first

problem for the people is Frontex, they spell [...] his name wrong so everywhere he goes it's difficult for him to fix his name... (Group Interview).

As already mentioned, according to Law 4375/2016, newly arrived persons should be directly transferred to a Reception and Identification Centre, where they are subject to a three-day “restriction of freedom within the premises of the centre”; this can be further extended for a maximum of 25 days if reception and identification procedures have not been completed. The restriction of freedom entails “the prohibition to leave the Centre and the obligation to remain in it”. After this period, newly arrived third-country nationals are obliged to remain on the island and to reside in the Hotspot facilities for an undetermined period of time, thus resulting in serious overcrowding (Petracou, 2018, p. 45).

Although Article 13(2) of Presidential Decree 220/2007 sets a maximum time limit of one year regarding permanence in accommodation centres, in practice this timeframe is often violated, as shown by a number of surveys such as a research led by the Greek Council for Refugees in 2014, which concludes that asylum-seekers often stay in reception centres for 18 months and even longer (AIDA, 2015, p. 69). According to research by the Danish Red Cross which took place at the RIC of Moria in Lesbos, the detainment of asylum-seekers can cause long-term effects on their mental health, whereas the negative impact of detention conditions tends to persist over time. Under these circumstances, that include the lack of basic resources and the risk of exploitation and violence, it is common for detained asylum-seekers to develop psychological symptoms such as hopelessness, self-harm, suicidal ideation, distress and a diminished sense of dignity and control, which in turn may lead to increased domestic violence.

The waiting period between one's arrival at Moria Hotspot and registration by EASO is not always the same for all cases. Some people mention being registered upon their arrival, while others many days later. Interviewee narratives regarding the procedure of registration with EASO reveal a common procedure of personal data registration. Nevertheless, negative experiences are reported in some cases, especially with refugees who have lost their documents and certificates during the journey or did not have any due to the specific conditions under which they fled their countries of origin. In yet other cases, actors did not accept the personal data provided by refugees, such as age, and registered them with other data than those provided.

I decided to go and get my documents by myself, in other countries, the borders were open, you would get a document from the police and the UNHCR in order to travel to the border legally. The official asked me how old I was, I said 27 and he said no, you're underaged, and he wrote down 16 and sent me to a reception facility for underaged refugees [...] This was not good, I wanted to continue and not stay here, I did not accept it. I didn't have a beard, and he wrote down I was 16 and sent me to a reception facility for underaged refugees in Kos (Amin).

As revealed from the above extract, in some cases actors did not accept the age provided by refugees. Provisions on age assessment are included in the Joint Ministerial Decision 1982/2016 of the Minister of the Interior and Administrative Reconstruction and the Minister of Health. They prescribe age assessment via a

macroscopic medical examination and, in case of doubt, assessment of the person's cognitive, behavioural and psychological development. In the Reception and Identification Centres, age assessment is often carried out by NGOs. Implementation issues related to age assessment have, in some cases, resulted in unaccompanied children being identified as adults and being placed in detention or the opposite, in adults being identified as minors (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 53).

Vulnerability Assessment:

As the Representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO mentioned “at this point, we speak of the right to vulnerability instead of the right to asylum”. The vulnerability assessment process is a process mainly concerning people who arrive in the North-eastern Aegean islands. Following the EU-Turkey Statement, the vulnerability assessment in the islands determines which of the two asylum procedures applicants will be referred to. People identified as vulnerable should enter the regular asylum procedure in Greece, as opposed to the Fast-Track Border Procedure, which aims at sending most people back to Turkey under the EU-Turkey Statement. They should also be provided with adequate living conditions which tend to their vulnerability. Additionally, in certain cases – usually the most vulnerable – the “geographical restriction” might be lifted and some might be transferred to apartments in the mainland. As already mentioned, following a change in practice in May 2017, Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability have their restriction lifted immediately, while non-Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability do not have their restriction lifted until they undergo the personal interview (AIDA, 2018, p. 121). This change in administrative practice as regards the lifting of the geographical restriction of vulnerable non-Syrian applicants has further exacerbated overcrowding on the islands (AIDA, 2018, p. 121). Generally speaking, however, the vulnerability assessment has an impact on the asylum procedure.

After completing procedures with Frontex and the police, refugees are subject to the first registration in the form of a “short interview” conducted mostly by EASO. The procedure that should be followed includes, firstly, a vulnerability screening by the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (known by its Greek acronym KEELPNO³) and, secondly, registration with EASO. In particular, the newly arrived persons are supposed to undergo a vulnerability assessment that includes assessment by a medical specialist and, if needed, by a psychologist. This is critical to ensure that vulnerable people – for instance pregnant women, unaccompanied children, people with disabilities and victims of torture or sexual violence – are identified and can access the protection and care they need.

Based on our participants, KEELPNO is yet another understaffed service with almost permanent problems and a severe shortage of interpreters and doctors. Therefore, it is considered unable to respond to the increased needs in the field. This results in a lack of access to medical assistance and significant delays with vulnerability assessments, which sometimes take place after the asylum interview.

³ KEELPNO is the responsible agency for medical screening and vulnerability assessment in the Hotspots

Despite the fact that the proper procedure is to first undergo the vulnerability assessment by KEELPNO and then be registered by EASO, a lot of interviewees mention that they were first registered by EASO and met with the doctor afterwards. Additionally, in most cases delays are mentioned regarding the appointments with KEELPNO since the arrival of the refugees at Moria Hotspot. The understaffing of KEELPNO and the increase in arrivals are some of the factors contributing to these delays.

But, normally, you could not go to EASO without seeing a doctor first, what's really wrong with your health, if you are healthy or not. You must see the doctor first (Willy).

-And what happened with the doctor, what did he ask?

-I told them I had been in prison, but I could not prove it in any way, you cannot get documents in Moria, I registered for asylum, others cannot be registered without the medical report, without the necessary certificates to go and register. When I went, I had nothing with me, I did it the other way around, I went right in, when I found my family, I decided that anything I did, I would do straight away, I would never again lie.

-So, you went to the doctor and told him you cannot prove you were in prison, but what happened with the doctor after all?

-I explained what had happened and he referred me, I showed him my back and my body, my scars, and he referred me to a psychiatrist.

-Did he give you a document that mentioned vulnerability?

-No, not to me, not to my wife or anyone.

-OK, did you go through EASO?

-[...] people see the doctor first and then EASO, but I went to EASO first and then to the doctor (Ahmed).

In most cases, refugees did not receive official information or counselling about the procedure that would follow and the importance of the KEELPNO diagnosis. Others were informed about vulnerability from their networks or other refugees that had already gone through a relevant experience.

Yes, I got the date of the interview, most of the people didn't know what to do, nobody talked about vulnerability if they were sick because the problem is even when they bring you to the doctor, you are afraid to tell him that you are sick because you don't know what will happen, maybe if you say you're sick they send you back in that moment. If you tell all of your health problems to the doctor you become vulnerable. It looks like other people they don't want us to know because, from the beginning, if you don't know nothing you screw yourself, it will be easier for them to deport you after (Penen).

-And there were some people including some questions and they mark yes if you are going to transfer to Athens and I didn't know who these people were and I talked to them, they were asking some questions only. And then when they mark yes, like, this is a pass for example, so that you will transfer to Athens, when they mark no...

-And in your case what happened?

-They said yes, they marked me as a yes and they told that I can go now to Athens. Yeah, when they did sign these papers and they marking yes, it means that I need the doctor and should be transferred to Athens, I should visit the

doctors. And if they mark no it means that this person doesn't have such a big problem and stays in Moria (Abdul).

Additionally, some informants mentioned that people seeking asylum often have no access to interpreters during their vulnerability assessments. Especially from the group interview with community leaders in Moria, it was revealed that one of the major problems with KEELPNO is the lack of interpreters:

The first problem is the asylum, KEELPNO is the first problem [...] KEELPNO is the first problem because they don't have [...] translators. When she goes over there, they'll give her one more time for 4 months later, then she'll go [...] one week later. So, the problem they face is translation. KEELPNO is not accepting any translator from inside Moria (Group Interview).

In other cases, refugees are not aware of the diagnosis of the vulnerability assessment, as it is not provided in a language they can understand.

- Before the interview they gave me appointment with doctor and I told them my problem and he gave me a paper and I took that paper to the interview, my interview.
- Do you know what he wrote in that paper, the doctor?
- No, no one else. Only they know.
- The paper is in Greek or in English?
- In Greek. It was... (Aynla).

Narratives regarding serious issues in the procedures during the vulnerability check at KEELPNO were mentioned by a lot of interviewees. Our interlocutors call the doctors responsible for the vulnerability assessment “yes/no doctors”.

- Did you, at the time of your registration, did you pass by the doctor?
- Yes.
- How was the process?
- Yes, there is the doctor, we call him yes/no doctor. All the refugees they know about him like that. That you get yes or no. If you get yes, it's ok, if you get no, you have to stay here.
- What does yes/no stand for?
- I think that is for health issue. There is this yes/no doctor, and there are those who have big problems so there is a psychiatrist doctor also. We call him doctor “asap”. “Asap” means brain. In the yes/no doctor, my brother was a minor and he got a yes because until then I hadn't taken his guardianship. So, he got yes, but there was a translator who was Iranian translator. I asked the doctor because I didn't understand his language, I didn't live in Iran, he said that he could speak in English in order to tell me. He said no, I don't know English. He was speaking English but, again, he said no. So, I requested two times that we change translator and if it was possible to find someone who speaks Dari. He said no. I don't know what the translator told me. I couldn't understand a single word. So, I got no at first. No means that you have to remain on this island (Fatima).

Last but not least, in Athens and the rest of the mainland there are no vulnerability assessments such as the ones conducted on the islands. Therefore, this process does not have an impact on the administrative procedure of the asylum demand.

Vulnerability on the mainland is something completely different from vulnerability on the islands.

In Athens, for example, you can only find the central offices of the Reception and Identification Service, which do not accept referrals, they do not examine cases. In Athens, it is up to the discretion of each caseworker of the Asylum Service to decide if the process should be interrupted and the asylum-seeker referred to an NGO whose certificates of vulnerability are recognised by the Asylum Service (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

However, in case of vulnerability and regardless if the applicant is on the islands or on the mainland, it is still important for him or her to have free access to legal aid in order to be supported and referred to a competent actor, one who can provide a vulnerability certification to be included as proof in the file that will be examined by the Asylum Service.

If, as I said, a person of concern comes to us to get help in preparing for the interview and mentions having suffered torture, we, as a legal aid program, will refer the person to the relevant NGO who shall verify if he or she is truly a victim of torture. After completing its corresponding protocol, the NGO shall issue a report; if the applicant is deemed a victim of torture on the basis of the Istanbul Protocol on torture, he or she shall be referred to a different NGO working in the field of mental rehabilitation for torture victims. We, as providers of legal aid, shall gather all the documents and certificates and submit them to the Asylum Service as complementary to all other evidence and the application. We shall ask for them to be included and considered in the judgement of the caseworker of the case, and request that the applicant be granted refugee status (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Asylum Procedures

It is estimated that access to asylum was extremely problematic until June 2013 and that things have started to improve slightly since 2013 and after the establishment of the Asylum Service (Law 3907/2011) as the competent state authority for examining applications for international protection at first instance. According to our participants from meso level interviews, the establishment of the Asylum Service as an autonomous civil service constitutes an important development for asylum procedures and protection policies in Greece.

The landmark year for Greece in the field of asylum is the year of salvation 2013. In June 2013, the Asylum Service is launched as we know it today, as an autonomous political service belonging to different ministries at different times (footnote: at the beginning it fell under the Ministry of Citizen Protection, then the Ministry of Migration Policy and now once again the Ministry of Citizen Protection) (Lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Prior to the establishment of the Asylum Service, there was no autonomous service to deal with the requests, and the police was the responsible authority for handling asylum requests. As a result, the applications were primarily subject to the will of the Hellenic police and, more specifically, of the Directorate of Political Asylum. While the police were in charge of examining asylum requests, the rate of refugee

status granting was virtually non-existent. Not only were most decisions negative/rejective but, more importantly, there was no justification provided for said rejection.

The justification provided for the rejection was virtually non-existent, copy-pasted from another case. If you looked at the interview minutes you realised, they were a case of copy-pasting from a different nationality, a different country, a different case (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

In 2013 there was a feeling of hope in the field of human rights, civil society and NGOs in general that this situation would change with the establishment of the Asylum Service. Unfortunately, it began to operate amidst the memoranda and the economic crisis in Greece and this had a direct impact on its understaffing. There was not enough personnel to staff the service but, rather, people hired on temporary contracts which were not always renewed; this, combined with the 2015 'refugee crisis' and the skyrocketing of arrivals, created the problem-ridden system that persists until today (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Difficulties regarding access to the asylum procedure have been observed since the Asylum Service began operating in 2013, mainly due to staff shortages and the non-operation of all RAOs provided for by law. The insufficiency of the Asylum Service has resulted in significant delays both in registering asylum demands and in issuing decisions, a fact that mentally and physically wears out asylum seekers. According to UNHCR, the average processing time at first instance is reported at about 8.5 months in 2018. In 80.5% of the total number of 58,793 applications pending as of the end of 2018, the interview has not yet taken place (UNHCR, 2018). Thus, asylum seekers are supposed to wait for months, if not more than a year, to have their asylum claims heard. This was reported by all interviewees from both the meso and micro level.

The challenge is dealing with the people. Because we came from a difficult situation and it's getting really hard for asylum procedure, for the asylum office to deal with this all. First of all, GAS and EASO didn't have much employees. Take the population of refugees in Lesbos, they are nothing compared to them. They need to increase the number of their employees. In every department. In the EU department, GAS should increase their employees, EASO should increase their employees, because 6000-7000 refugees for maximum 30 employees are like unfair. For me I think they increase their employees. Then they can approach people easily, then they can accelerate the cases easily. Now people are waiting for the decision eight months. If they increase their employees, maybe they can wait for less, like four months maximum. Now people are waiting for eight months, nine months, ten months or more than a year (Robel).

For some people takes a year and a half, for some others one year and for other people eight months. For me it took... from the day that I arrived, I arrived 6th of July 2016 and I finished my asylum procedure in November 2017. After you lose your time here, one year, why they give you a rejection... It's not only my question, almost all of them, all of the people inside... Whatever the decision, all of them want their decision soon and as we hear in other countries, they did it, they inform you if they accept you or they do not accept you (Robel).

That is the main thing, even if today the Greek government decides to build five-star hotels with everything inside... but if the procedure doesn't change, people will still have a problem, because the big problem, that most of the refugees call it "perimene" [the Greek word for 'wait']. Why you wait so long for uncertain future? If you pass your interview within 5 or 6 months, they will not give you a result and you'll say give me an answer and that is no answer, seven, eight months. You say no, you won't become crazy, let me find a lawyer to see what's happening, you go to the lawyer and the lawyer will tell you OK my friend, did you pass your interview? Yes. So, there is nothing we can do, you need to wait more for the results. The future becomes uncertain, everything will be dark in front of you and now you become frustrated, anxious, stressed. You don't sleep at night, you become angry. Inside here people they become more crazy, violent (Penen).

According to our interviewees, access to the asylum procedure for an applicant is still a structural and endemic problem in Greece. Although progress has been made, significant challenges remain in the national asylum system, giving rise to major protection and safety risks.

Everyone speaks about the conditions in Moria, the toilets, the water, the food, things are not good in Moria, but this is not the most important problem. Even if they accommodate us in hotels and nice places, people will have the same problems, people would keep becoming mad, if the Asylum System was the same. They want you to collapse in order to ask by yourself to go back...it's a kind of fight (Penen).

Many persons who wish to lodge an application are unable to have their application registered within a given day. Refugee communities report cases of asylum-seekers presenting themselves up to 30 times before managing to register their asylum application (UNHCR, 2014) and this has been reported both for the mainland and the Aegean islands. The increased influx of asylum-seekers waiting outside the several Regional Asylum Offices in Athens cannot be handled by the already understaffed Asylum Service.

Another huge problem for asylum-seekers is to even access the area of the Asylum Service. If you do not have a lawyer it is very difficult, and you will probably never get through the door. This is plain to see if one goes by Katechaki... there are people piling up from 3 am in hope of managing to get in before 7 am (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

If one passes by the Central Asylum Office in Athens, one will observe people not only waiting in long queues but actually sleeping in front of the entrance for days trying to get through the door. As a lawyer employed in national and international agencies mentioned, "it is extremely difficult to get into the courtyard of the Asylum Service and conduct any kind of business, even renew your asylum-seeker card".

The people waiting for their turn come from various areas of Greece and belong to different legal statuses: vulnerable asylum-seekers coming from the Eastern Aegean islands after having the geographical restriction lifted, registered or unregistered people coming from the Evros region, as well as asylum-seekers with scheduled interviews or others who simply want to renew their asylum card.

Even though the Asylum Service has been implementing a system for arranging appointments to register asylum applications through Skype since 2014, the problem has not been solved.

It should also be noted that, for a person to apply for asylum in the mainland or have his or her will to apply for asylum registered by the Asylum Service, he or she must go through a Skype appointment. This means that one must be familiarised with the internet, know what it means to make an appointment via Skype, have access to the internet or to an Internet Corner or an NGO that can provide this. Very often people cannot get connected and remain unregistered. And this is very dangerous, as it is very possible they might run into a police control and find themselves in administrative detention in Amygdaleza, even though they have been making systematic attempts to arrange an appointment with the Asylum Service and have their demand registered (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

In addition to the current pending asylum requests, there is also a large and continuing backlog of unresolved cases under the old procedure with decisions that have been pending for years; this number is expected to continue increasing in the future.

There is a huge backlog of unresolved cases. By 'backlog' I mean accumulated cases that are still in limbo, and people have been waiting for years for a decision and simply renew their asylum-seeker cards (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Last but not least, it has been noted that, due to the large number of asylum requests and in order to tackle the urgency of the situation, the Asylum Service operates not only according to the existing legislation but also, to a large extent, to internal instructions issued in cooperation with various involved state actors, such as the police and the RIS.

Differentiations emerge every day, as the Asylum Service now essentially operates on directives; that is, it might receive specific instructions such as the so-called pilot scheme implemented by the police. Some people are arrested upon arrival because they originate from countries with a low recognition rate... mostly Pakistan, Bangladesh, Morocco, Algeria, many African countries. If examined on a case-by-case basis, many of these people have left their country for a reason, a very serious reason in many cases, and many also have documents to support their claims. They are kept in pre-removal centres on the islands and apply for asylum while in detention. But this is not done in compliance with a specific law, it is simply a practice that is implemented to make things easier for the Asylum Service, which is having a hard time processing all the pending demands, or ease the way for returns as provided for by the EU-Turkey Statement. However, all this cannot stand from a legal point of view, just as the Statement cannot stand either (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Transformations in Second instance

The changes that took place in the operation of the Appeals Authority in 2016 are considered to have had a negative impact on the asylum procedures. In accordance with Law 4375/2016, as opposed to 3907/2011, the Independent Appeals Committees review the request from the file. That is, the applicant is not entitled to a second interview unless very specific conditions are met.

If, for example, there are indications that the first-instance interview was incomplete, if the lawyer submits new evidence, that is, if the applicant has new things to say that were not said in the first instance and if, of course, it can be proven that they were not deceitfully withheld and emerged at a later date, then and only then might the interview be repeated (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Our research showed that, until the first half of the operation of the Appeals Authority in 2013, it was at each Appeals Committee's discretion whether or not to invite the applicant to an interview, even without the recommendation of the rapporteur. According to our informants, this changed after the passing of Law 4375/2016, after which all appeals are examined based on the case file. Decisions in second instance are reached by majority; however, the opinion of the minority is also taken down.

You examine the file and the statement of grounds. If the person has legal aid, you also look at the statement of grounds submitted by the lawyer, as well as if all the organisations involved in the procedure have operated correctly, if there is a vulnerability assessment, by which actor, etc. Each demand must be examined on a case-by-case basis. This is the key to success for all stages of the procedure. And by case-by-case basis I mean on the basis of the person you are dealing with, his or her profile, the objective facts of his or her case, what the present situation in the country of origin is; you do not base yourself on stereotypes such as, e.g., he is from Pakistan, so he is an economic migrant. Your main tool is obviously COI, this is what you work with, but not stereotypically (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Lastly, serious concerns have also been raised by some of our meso level informants on the composition of the Independent Appeals Committees. According to Law 4375/2016, the Independent Appeals Committees are also composed of three members; however, unlike the members of the Appeals Committees designated by Law 3907/2011, two are first-instance administrative judges and the third member is designated by the UNHCR.

So, to what extent can a judge, a state official who is also the competent decision-making authority in the third instance, participate in the second-instance administrative appeal? Judges are called to pass judgement in the third instance, in the demand for annulment before the administrative court, that is, when the asylum demand has been rejected in second instance (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

It is believed that reforms in the composition of the committees resulted in a sharp increase of negative decisions in the second instance.

99 percent of the decisions issued now in second instance are negative due to the legal provisions that changed the composition of the committees; they are

now made up of judges and one UNHCR representative; that is why so many appeals have been rejected this way (representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO).

Recognition rates at the appeal level remain significantly low. Out of the total in-merit decisions issued in 2018, 2.8% granted refugee status, 1.5% subsidiary protection, 4.5% referred the case for humanitarian protection and 91% were negative. This may be an alarming finding as to the operation of an efficient and fair asylum procedure in Greece (AIDA, 2019a).

Additionally, second-instance decisions issued by the Independent Appeals Committees for Syrian applicants systematically uphold the first-instance inadmissibility decisions if no vulnerability is identified (AIDA, 2019a).

Furthermore, there is a significant backlog of undecided cases at the stage of appeal which were not handed over to the new Appeals Authority in June 2013 but were maintained by the ‘old’ Appeals Committees. Of particular concern is the backlog of 37,482 undecided appeal cases dating back to the 30th of September 2014, which were decided on in the first instance under the old system. This backlog includes cases that have been pending examination for a considerable amount of time, some for more than seven years. The significance of the backlog lies in the fact that, due to the serious deficiencies in the previous police-run first instance procedure, examination at the appeal stage represents, for the majority of applicants, the only opportunity to have their claims fairly assessed (UNHCR, 2014).

The Family Reunification Application Process:

The implementation of the family reunification process is marked by serious systemic failures intrinsic to complex national approaches in sending and receiving states. In this context, the role of the lawyer appears to be of pivotal importance for the progress of the process. Among the problematic practices on a procedural level, particularly relevant is the lack of detailed reasoning in refusal letters, vague negative responses without an assessment of and reference to the evidence previously submitted or without a request for the required evidence by the respondent State.

Since March 2016 and after the adoption of Law 4375/2016, the entire framework of the Dublin Regulation and, more specifically, of Family Reunifications has been defined. As mentioned in a previous chapter, according to article 60 of Law 4375/2016, vulnerable cases as well as applicants for family reunification are supposedly excluded from the Fast Track Border Procedure.

The Dublin Regulation has two types of articles, those pertaining to mandatory law and others that pertain to optional humanitarian law, the so-called humanitarian clause. There are many asylum demands that do not leave under mandatory law alone but also in accordance with the humanitarian clause. For example, the humanitarian clause dictates that if I am the daughter of Zainab, of Afghan origin and aged 18, therefore an adult daughter, I am not referred according to the Dublin mandatory law. However, I could be referred under humanitarian law if my mother has a serious illness, is not self-sufficient and is proven to depend on her daughter, who must also be proven capable of

providing her mother with the necessary means for her subsistence (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

The issue is that it has been observed that demands referring to the humanitarian clause are not being sent from the islands. In fact, it remains at the discretion of each caseworker to inform the National Dublin Unit on demands for the application of the humanitarian clause, although these demands should be judged by the National Dublin Unit, the Asylum Service body that is competent for deciding if they fall within the scope of the law. This cannot be predetermined by the RAO or caseworker that happens to be examining the case (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Another issue that arises is that of requests for family reunification that are considered 'overdue' by the country to which the request is sent. Germany, in particular, considers requests for family reunification sent after the three months' period following the asylum request has expired as overdue and does not even take them into account.

An applicant for family reunification is supposed to apply within three months of the date on which the asylum demand has been lodged. However, due to the crucial issues affecting the Asylum Service, there are protracted delays in sending the asylum claim on time to the different Member States. As a result, several claims are sent beyond the set time limit; the responsibility does not lie with the applicant but exclusively with the Asylum Service. As a lawyer employed in national and international agencies mentioned, "there is no way one can declare one's will to apply for asylum and have his or her demand registered within three months. Thus, time limits are very often exceeded. Moreover, some claims are considered unfounded by other Member States, especially Germany.

Let's take the example of a family from Afghanistan: both spouses are in Greece (and are registered as asylum-seekers in Greece) while their underaged child has been irregularly sent to Germany. The child goes to Germany alone and applies for family reunification there, as a minor who has been separated from his family. If the parents residing in Greece apply, through their lawyer, to be reunited with their child in Germany, this is now considered an unfounded demand, whereas it was something quite common in 2015 (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

A long-awaited Joint Ministerial Decision was issued in August 2018 on the requirements regarding the issuance of visas for family members in the context of the family reunification of refugees. However, administrative obstacles which hinder the effective exercise of the right to family reunification for refugees persist (AIDA, 2019a).

The impact of the EU-Turkey Statement:

The EU-Turkey Statement has had significant repercussions for Greece, not least of which the creation of two separate asylum procedures and crucial changes in the national legal framework. The regular procedure now applies to those on the mainland and outside the scope of the deal, and a separate "Fast Track Border Procedure"

applies to those on the islands, in order to implement the deal and particularly the returns. Since the EU-Turkey Statement, newly arrived persons are not allowed to leave the islands before a decision on the admissibility of their cases is taken. The admissibility procedure prevents access to international protection by introducing an additional administrative step preceding the substantive examination of asylum applications. If Turkey is considered a safe third country or first country of asylum, claims are rejected as inadmissible and the person concerned can be returned to Turkey (ECCHR, 2019).

The legal basis for the possibility of a return to Turkey can be found in the EU recast Asylum Procedures Directive (APD) and specifically in the concept of “first country of asylum” and the concept of “safe third country” through an admissibility procedure (Directive 2013/32/EU of the 26th of June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (Council Directive 2013/32/EU).

Importantly, at the time of the EU-Turkey Statement, Greece had not transposed the recast APD. Thus, neither concept was inscribed in Greek law, although both were implied. So, the government quickly introduced a new law (Law 4375/2016) before Parliament on the 30th of March, transposing the APD but also legally covering the operation of the Hotspots (Dimitriadi, 2016).

Regarding the EU-Turkey Statement, serious concerns have been raised by our participants. Firstly, it is noted that the statement lacks legal status due to the fact that it does not relate to any directive, regulation or contract.

As of March 2016, the Statement applies. We are essentially faced with the deconstruction of asylum and of the Geneva Convention and the overall field of rights as we know it. The Statement is a statement, it has no legal status, neither is it a proper directive or regulation or convention, it is simply an agreement. However, we must understand that the granting of asylum is not an act of humanity, it is an administrative act, an administrative action of the state. It is the right and the obligation of the state to give asylum to whoever fulfils the corresponding conditions and criteria. It is not at the discretion of a philanthropist or of civil society, neither is it a luxury. It is a contractual obligation resulting from international and European law documents that have been incorporated and transcribed into Greek law and now constitute compulsory law, such as the 1951 Geneva Convention, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Istanbul Protocol, etc. (lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

The changes taking place in the asylum procedures after the EU-Turkey Statement seem to be significant and negative. Until 2015 and despite the long delays in the asylum procedures, things are considered to have been much better in terms of human rights. An important change is the fact that:

Until 2015 there was a regular procedure in the Greek asylum offices which basically examined the essence of each case, whether a person had the right to be granted asylum in Greece and whether the reasons for which this person left his or her country grant the refugee status or the right to international protection. After the Statement, EASO came into play, essentially to examine whether new arrivals can be sent back to Turkey. Most decisions issued both then and now

were and are negative as to the granting of asylum in Greece. The difference is that, in 2015, many people did not apply for asylum, everyone tried to move on. People would come to Greece and then continue their journey (given that the borders were open). However, once the EU-Turkey Statement was in place, they could be immediately sent back if they did not apply for asylum; this resulted in a 100 percent increase in asylum demands (representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO).

The upgrade of the role of EASO in the National Asylum Procedures and the cooperation with the Greek Asylum System (GAS)

EASO is a European Agency established in 2010 with the scope of supporting Member States in providing international protection. As such, it plays a crucial role in the EU border regime and asylum system. Specifically, in Greece, EASO operates a plan involving support to the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement (EASO, 2016).

In the Greek national asylum system and since the introduction of the EU-Turkey statement, EASO has been mainly involved in the admissibility procedure⁴ of international protection applications submitted at the Greek Hotspots. EASO conducts interviews, drafts opinions and recommends decisions to the Greek Asylum Service (EASO, 2016).

During these interviews, EASO agents assess whether applicants should be exempted or not from the admissibility procedure and transferred out of the Hotspots due to vulnerability reasons.

Specifically, EASO’s concluding remarks specify whether the safe third country concept may be applied in a particular case, and thereby provide the ground on which an application can be rejected as inadmissible. It is common practice for the Greek Asylum Service to rely on EASO records without posing any direct questions to the applicant. Under those circumstances, the decision of the Greek Asylum Service is bound to heavily rely not only on EASO decision-making as to the conduct of the interview itself, but also on the final recommendation of EASO on admissibility. Therefore, EASO officers exercise de facto power over decisions relating to applications for international protection by conducting admissibility interviews and making recommendations (ECCHR, 2019).

Since recent Law 4540/2018, the role of EASO in the national asylum system has been upgraded and expanded from assessing vulnerability, conducting interviews and drafting opinions in border procedures to similar competencies in the regular procedure.

The significant influence of EASO within the joint procedures at the Hotspots is all the more concerning given the persistence of systematic failures in the conduct of

⁴ The admissibility procedure prevents access to international protection by introducing an additional administrative step preceding the substantive examination of asylum applications. If Turkey is considered a safe third country or first country of asylum, claims are rejected as inadmissible and the person concerned can be returned to Turkey.

interviews by EASO officials. In its work with asylum-seekers at Hotspots on the Greek islands, EASO has violated fundamental standards for asylum interviews and overstepped its competences under European law. As the Representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO mentioned, “there have been many complaints on the way EASO conduct the interviews, both in terms of interpreting and in that they put too much pressure on people”.

EASO admissibility interviews have been reported by many of our participants. According to their personal experience, interviews with EASO lack a fair hearing and careful consideration of their individual case and need for protection. As interviewee Penen mentioned “the biggest problem is EASO and the Asylum System. No one speaks about the Asylum System and EASO. The process is like torture, 4-8 hours and the next day again”.

EASO, they just blame people. They always blame the people for not waiting. All people are waiting. People have been waiting for one-two years. For you it's nothing. Because you work in the day and you go home in the night. But we are there 24/7. We are the ones who are dealing with the situation. You are dealing, but you are getting payed, it's your job. So, they are always blaming people, which is not appropriate. Which makes people more aggressive. Instead of saying sorry, apologising, blaming them, you know, so no one will like it. In general [...] this is how they deal with people. EASO, they need to change their nature, they need to change some procedures in the way they talk with people. The nature is not so nice. They are one of the unorganised organisations I can say I have ever seen in my life (Kingslot).

The interview I did with EASO about Turkey, they lost it. On the 1st of March 2017 I gave my interview, 12th of March I was supposed to take my transcript, the copy of my interview, they gave me and interview date, I thought it was my second interview but on the next day when I went there, actually they were asking the same questions which I had already answered on the 1st of March. So, they lost it and they were blaming me. When I finished my interview, I requested a transcript, they gave me a piece of paper that this date, after this day you can come and pick your transcript and on the day you saw the paper and they will give it to you. So, I showed the paper and told them that I already gave the interview, this is the proof that I asked for my transcript. They started blaming me, that from where did you get this, and I said from this office, from your colleagues... But they thought that it was fake. And then I gave another interview, because when I started arguing for my right, they said that I have two options. Either you go back to Afghanistan or you are going to give us an interview. That's how they talk to people, instead of saying maybe they lost it, but sorry about the mistake, no, they don't accept any mistake, they don't take any blame on them. They just blame people (Kingslot).

According to our participants and existing reports, EASO officers often stick to a rigid questionnaire without giving the applicant room to elaborate on his or her personal history of harm or persecution (ECCHR, 2019).

She said that it is me who is doing the questions and you answer. And if she feels that she doesn't like the answer that you are giving, she will tell you, you didn't give me an answer. And after I told I have the right to answer the question

or not? Now you tell me that I must, because you ask me one question but in a different way. I went inside four times. I started the first interview at eight o'clock until half past two p.m., but most of the time she was interrupting me. Four to five times she interrupted me (Penen).

Moreover, during the interviews, except for the overwhelming number of closed questions, EASO officers often fail to give applicants the opportunity to clarify inconsistencies between their statements and information from other sources.

I understood she Googled it because she had a computer in front of her. I'm telling you my life, my experience, but you want to correct my experience with these Google things? I'm telling you the truth, if you think that you can find everything that I'm telling you now for my life in Google, why am I here? Put my name and Google it and find all my stories. Inside my interview it was horrible. It's like when the police investigate something, and they arrest you and they want to know the truth. They bring you to the police station, they put you somewhere nobody can see. Sometimes they abuse us, they give you a paper that says the day of your interview. If they call your name you must bring the paper, but people can't read this paper because it's in English and not everybody speaks English. Most of the people speak African, Arabic, and you're writing with small characters down on the paper that you can have a lawyer, you will not even see it, I saw it after spending three months in interviews (Penen).

Access to Information and Legal assistance

Law 4375/2016 (art. 41), following the Asylum Procedures Directive, provides *inter alia* that asylum-seekers should be informed on the procedure to be followed, their rights and obligations in a language they understand. Despite this legislation, a wide range of information gaps were reported by interviewees.

As a rule, and upon newcomers' transfer to the RICs, the RIS undertakes their initial briefing on rights and obligations, which is then followed-up by a second information session conducted by UNHCR field-based teams (usually 10-15-minute group sessions). Newcomers are frequently provided with information too soon after their arrival, a few hours after their rescue at sea, at a time when they are usually too exhausted, frustrated and usually not in a position to understand the information provided. Additionally, despite the fact that a number of actors are engaged in providing information concerning the asylum procedure at the North-eastern Aegean islands, there is still a serious lack of information, mainly due to the lack of interpretation. Moreover, access to information remains a serious matter of concern also due to the complexity of the procedure and the constantly changing legislation and practice, as well as bureaucratic hurdles.

From the micro level interviews that we conducted, we observed that very often our informants didn't know exactly in which step of the procedure they were. Additionally, they often confused the registration by EASO with the Asylum Interview. In other cases, they couldn't understand the meaning of the status they had gained or their relevant rights.

-I received the answer of my interview yesterday. My decision.
-And what's your status now?
-My status is... I can't memorise, can I read it to you? My status is subsidiary protection (not clear). It's (not clear), not refugee (Aynla).

We assume that one of the reasons is the serious lack of interpretation in RIS and even more in pre-removal detention centres, where access to information is even more limited.

According to a UNHCR interagency participatory assessment in 2018 based on a sample of 1,436 persons:

The majority of participants were frustrated with what they consider a lack of sufficient information on asylum procedures and the legal framework. A particular source of anxiety is the lack of clarity on procedures or feedback on the status of their asylum claim, particularly on the islands. This has severe implications on psycho-social wellbeing, irrespective of age and gender. [...] Participants in most Focus Group Discussions noted difficulties accessing information. This included a lack of interpreters for certain languages (e.g. Somali, Farsi, Kurmanji, Panjabi, Bangla, Urdu, Sorani, Amharic, Tigrinya, etc.), lack of consistent and simplified information on services and procedures. This applies to sites, RICs and urban locations and to information provision upon arrival. [...] Communication materials are often too difficult to understand or not translated in all relevant languages (UNHCR, 2018).

Despite the fact that interviewees mention the need for legal assistance and counselling almost during the entire asylum procedure, free legal aid is officially provided to applicants only in appeal procedures before the Appeals Authority, as indicated by Law 4375/2016, art. 44. Following this legal framework, a state-funded legal aid scheme on the basis of a list managed by the Asylum Service was put in place for the first time in Greece in September 2017. The legal aid scheme employed 21 lawyers; by the end of 2018, the number had gone up to 31. In March 2019, the Asylum Service issued a call for the list to be supplemented by 20 lawyers in different places in the country.

“According to Ministerial Decision 12205/2016 regulating the state-funded legal aid scheme, asylum-seekers must request legal aid at least 10 days before the date of examination of the appeal under the regular procedure, while shorter time limits are foreseen for the Admissibility Procedure, Accelerated Procedure and Fast-Track Border Procedure. If a legal representative has not been appointed at the latest 5 days before the examination of the appeal under the regular procedure, the applicant may request a postponement of the examination” (AIDA, 2018, p. 57).

You will go to the Asylum Service at the Katechaki RAO, you will apply for asylum and they will say “do you want a lawyer?”, “yes”, “this way” or you will be rejected at first instance and you will say “I want to appeal”, “do you have a lawyer?”, “no”, “would you want one? This way”. This will be the situation a priori all over a Greece in the second instance. By extension, it must happen in the first instance, but it will take a lot of time until this registry can be ready (Lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

Despite this positive development, the capacity of the legal aid scheme remains limited and most appellants in 2018 did not have access to it. “Out of a total of 15,355 appeals lodged in 2018, only 3,351 (21.8%) asylum-seekers benefited from the state-funded legal aid scheme” (AIDA, 2018, p. 58). No state-funded legal aid is provided for other procedures regarding the asylum application, including the examination of the application at first instance and the judicial review of second-instance decisions. Given that legal aid is provided by law only for appeal procedures and remains limited in practice, applicants often have to navigate the complex asylum system on their own, without sufficient information.

Additionally, asylum-seekers have the right to consult, at their own cost, a lawyer or other legal advisor on matters relating to their application, according to L. 4375/2016 (art. 44). A significant number of NGOs provide legal advice and legal assistance in asylum procedures, usually based on the availability and their presence throughout the country. Over 10,000 asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection received services such as counselling, assistance and legal representation in asylum procedures and other issues relating to access to rights by NGOs under UNHCR funding in 2018 (AIDA, 2018, pp. 55-56).

Specifically, in Lesvos and until June 2017, according to a DRC report (2017), METAdrasi, an NGO providing interpreting services and legal support, was funded to provide free legal assistance at the appeals stage in Moria. Nevertheless, since the 1st of August 2017, NGOs providing legal aid reduced their presence due to a shift of EU funding from NGOs to the Greek government, leaving a substantial gap in legal assistance to asylum seekers on the island (DRC, 2017). According to our interviewees of the meso level, this cutback in funding has affected the whole legal aid program implemented by the NGOs and, at this point in time, there is no free legal aid in the Eastern Aegean islands or on the mainland, with the exception of a few NGO staff who are under functioning.

Regarding legal aid to detainees, lawyers from different NGOs (e.g. the Greek Council for Refugees) occasionally visit specific pre-removal centres in the country to provide information on asylum procedures and register their will to apply for asylum. The same procedure is followed by UNHCR, that is, they visit pre-removal centres and register detainees who wish to apply for asylum, while IOM record those interested in voluntary returns. Additionally, when these NGOs find vulnerability cases under detention, they raise objections against the detention and report the violation of relevant laws.

The provision of information on asylum is very important, because there are no interpreters in the pre-removal centres, the only ones presented are the actors responsible for the detention, who in the best of cases don't speak English fluently; thus, communication is difficult, if not absent. So, information and legal aid is crucial, and the most important is to take down one's will to apply for asylum. Because if, for example, I am in detention and I want to say “asylum”, a police officer should pay attention, this shouldn't happen during the change of his shift when he is in a rush, my will should be registered in a book and a database. Fortunately, since 2015, the electronic database of the Asylum Service is connected to that of the Hellenic police, so a will to apply for asylum expressed by detainees is supposedly registered in this database. Before, that

registration used to be written by hand and it would usually go missing or get forgotten in a drawer (Lawyer employed in national and international agencies).

A significant part of the interviewees claim they did not have any help from a lawyer during the asylum process. Those who were assisted by a lawyer narrate their dissatisfaction from the services provided. Additionally, some had managed to gather information through their social networks, friends or other refugees who had already gone through the relevant procedures.

-You went for your asylum interview, before that did you receive any help from any lawyer?

-No, I didn't get help from anyone.

-Did you have any information about how the process was inside, did anyone inform you?

-Yes, my friend who arrived here before me, he told me some things. He gave me some information (Aynla).

-I didn't know something like that, I just waited for my date and I was just thinking how to leave this place, and then I said to myself OK, what is really going on here.

- You said you didn't have any info.

- No, I didn't, because even if you're a specialist they won't listen to you. I said I know nothing, but in the camp, refugees talk about those things, people that came before us were explaining to us how things are, but I didn't pay attention because they are also refugees. I needed somebody who's a specialist on those things to explain to me, but I didn't get a chance to meet one, I just went like that (Penen).

Detention

As mentioned, asylum-seekers are also detained in pre-removal detention centres together with third-country nationals under removal procedures, as provided in Article 31 of Law 3907/2011. Although pre-removal detention centres have been operating since 2012, they were officially established through Joint Ministerial Decisions in January 2015. Eight pre-removal detention centres are active in Greece. This includes six centres on the mainland (Amygdaleza, Tavros, Corinth, Xanthi, Paranesti, Fylakio in Evros region) and two on the islands (Lesvos, Kos). The total pre-removal detention capacity is 6,417 places (AIDA, 2019b).

Apart from the aforementioned pre-removal facilities and despite commitments from the Greek authorities to phase out such practices, third-country nationals, including asylum-seekers and unaccompanied children, are also detained in police stations and special holding facilities. The conditions of administrative detention in Greece have been systematically reported as seriously problematic and with important deficiencies in terms of hygiene, medical support and interpretation (AIDA, 2018; Humans Rights Watch, 2018).

As reports and press publications on Greece's immigration detention practices point out, there are several related concerns regarding the country's resistance to using alternatives to detention. The practices observed include the systematic detention of

children, the issuing of detention orders that lack individual assessments, inadequate conditions of detention and often the use of police stations for immigration detention purposes (GDP, 2019). A number of the Geneva-based treaty bodies have also criticised Greece's practices. For example, the UN Human Rights Committee (2015) urged Greece to ensure that all detention decisions are based on the individual circumstances of the person and to consider less invasive means to achieve the same end (OHCHR, 2015).

According to the official website of the Greek Asylum Service, asylum-seekers who are under detention by the police or in a Reception and Identification Centre and wish to apply for international protection (asylum) must inform the police officers or the staff of the Reception and Identification Centre, who will then inform the Asylum Service of this, and the full registration of the application will be scheduled. Additionally, on the day of the full registration asylum-seekers should be transferred to the nearest Regional Asylum Office or should be fully registered by an Asylum Unit operating in the facility where they are detained (Asylum Service, 2019).

However, as mentioned above, the significant challenges in accessing the asylum system mean that many persons who are potentially in need of international protection are unable to lodge a claim for international protection before they are placed in pre-removal detention (UNHCR, 2014).

In practice, people who apply for asylum while in detention remain there at least until their asylum application is registered, a process that is likely to take months (GDP, 2019). According to official data, asylum-seekers in pre-removal detention wait on average up to four months for the registration of their application for international protection (UNHCR, 2017).

Although the Greek Asylum Service has increased its capacity to register and examine applications for international protection by asylum-seekers who are in pre-removal detention centres, there is still a registration backlog. As a consequence, a considerable number of those who want to seek asylum but are unable to register in a timely manner or at all, remain exposed to the risk of removal and, potentially, refoulement (UNHCR, 2014).

Last but not least, in line with the Joint Action Plan on the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement, which recommended an increase in detention capacity on the islands, a "pilot project" known as the "**Low-Profile Scheme**" has also been implemented in Lesbos, Kos and partly Leros since 2017 (AIDA, 2019b). The "Low Profile Scheme" refers to a highly systematised and arbitrary practice of detention which is not legally defined in the legislation. Newcomers belonging to particular nationalities, whose country of origin has low recognition rates in the EU (such as people from N. Africa, Algeria, Morocco, Egypt, sub-Saharan countries, the Sahel, Pakistan and Bangladesh), are immediately placed in administrative detention upon completion of RIS procedures and remain there for the entire asylum procedure (GCR, 2018). During our research and specifically during the roundtable discussion organised by our research team at the university of the Aegean, the "Low-Profile Scheme" project was characterised by most of our meso level participants as a discriminatory

“containment policy” that functions as a new norm for Greece and a pilot project for the entire EU.

Readmissions to Turkey

According to the General Police Directorate of the Northern Aegean, “the readmission process is a process implemented by the Hellenic Police and Frontex”. People can be readmitted either from Lesbos or from Kos, as they are the only islands disposing of pre-removal detention (“Prokeka”) facilities.

During our fieldwork in Lesbos, we faced serious difficulties in gathering information regarding readmissions. Readmissions from Lesbos normally take place on a weekly basis, but this is subject to changes as there might be cancellations due to weather conditions, public holidays and insufficient numbers of people to be readmitted.

The police arrange the readmissions in prior agreement with Turkey, and the ombudsperson closely monitors the process. UNHCR also receives information at a central level on the planned readmissions; however, this only includes the profile of people to be readmitted, not personal details. As a result, in practice, it remains unclear who will be readmitted until the very last moment, as legal actors might proceed to legal remedies a few minutes prior to departure. However, major legal actors have the confidential information of these profiles – or even the names of the persons to be readmitted – at their disposal and act accordingly when it comes to one of their beneficiaries.

Between March 2016 and September 2019, 1914 persons were returned from the Aegean islands to Turkey in line with the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement. The majority were nationals of Pakistan (38%). Syrians make up 18% of the total returnees, followed by Algerians, Afghans and Bangladeshi nationals. In total, 351 Syrians have returned to Turkey so far. Of these, 38 returned after their second-degree asylum application was rejected. Of the total number of returnees, 45% did not express any intention to apply for asylum or withdrew their asylum application at a later stage (MOPOCP, 2019a).

Due to the low statistics, the European Commission (2017) has argued in a relevant press release regarding the progress of the EU-Turkey Statement that the pace of returns from Greece to Turkey is too slow and suggested that “significant additional efforts are still needed to reduce the backlog of asylum applications, address the insufficient pre-return processing and detention capacity in Greece in order to improve returns” (European Commission, 2018).

The Pre-Removal Centre of Moria, “PROKEKA”

Regarding Lesbos, the pre-removal detention centre of Moria, “PROKEKA”, was initially established in 2015 and reopened in mid-2017. The centre is located inside the Hotspot facility. In a meeting held with the General Police Directorate of the Northern Aegean, we were informed that “the Hellenic police operates within PROKEKA, as it is

its responsibility, its service". Therefore, PROKEKA operates under the responsibility of the Hellenic police and, therefore, "whoever is detained there is transferred and goes everywhere escorted by the police, even if it is inside Moria camp".

Additionally, the General Police Directorate of the Northern Aegean informed us that, in observance of Law 4375/2016, health units (Anonymous Health Units, AEMY) meant to provide psychosocial and medical support operate inside the PROKEKA.

There is a contract under law with the Anonymous Health Units and, at this moment, there are social workers, psychologists and an administrative secretary within the pre-removal centre. However, there is a problem, we still don't have a doctor and nurses. For the time being, this service is being provided by KEELPNO and the Mytilene Hospital (General Peripheral Police Directorate of the Northern Aegean).

Therefore, the AEMY are another national service facing serious understaffing and, as a result, are unable to effectively implement their scope and support detainees in Lesvos.

The General Police Directorate of the Northern Aegean refused to inform us on how many people were detained at the time of our discussion, claiming that it is internal information of the Hellenic Police. During the same period, an employee of an international agency that closely monitors the protection of asylum-seekers in Greece reported that "there is not a fixed number of people in PROKEKA, as this is subject to the constant changes of policies. For example, there are currently 25 people, while 3 months ago there were around 145 people".

The same participant also spoke of a serious lack in interpretation services inside Lesvos PROKEKA and reported that detainees are not provided with an adequate supply of hygiene products; as a result, conditions inside the centre remain seriously problematic.

Protection issues for recognised refugees

Despite the fact that Directive 2013/33/EU sets minimum standards for the reception conditions of applicants for international protection, beneficiaries of international protection (recognised refugees) are afforded no such guarantees. According to Presidential Decree 141/2013, beneficiaries of international protection should enjoy the same rights as Greek citizens and receive the necessary social assistance, according to the terms applicable to Greek citizens. Nevertheless, administrative and bureaucratic barriers, the lack of state-organised actions in order to address their particular situation, the non-effective implementation of the law, the general shrinking of the welfare system and the impact of the economic crisis prevent international protection holders from the enjoyment of their rights. For example, the recently established KEA (Social Solidarity Income) as a financial assistance offered by the Greek state to the most vulnerable groups (including Greeks, immigrants and refugees) requires a wide range of documents, such as a Tax Registration Number (AFM), a Social Security Number (AMKA), a bank account, a copy of an electronic

lease agreement and other papers that are not always easily accessible for the recognised refugees. The same applies for a number of other social benefits that could apply to recognised refugees but, still, specific limitations prevent the latter from gaining access to them⁵. Based on this prevailing situation, we could argue that being recognised as a refugee means having limited access to protection and social support.

Additionally, in terms of accommodation and housing for recognised refugees as a basic human right, specific recent developments raise serious concerns. The UNHCR accommodation scheme “ESTIA”, which began as a relocation scheme, today provides accommodation in apartments (mainly in the urban space) and cash assistance to applicants that meet specific vulnerability criteria. For a significant number of beneficiaries who were granted refugee status during their accommodation at ESTIA, a transitional period of some months was agreed in mid-2017, during which recognised refugees could remain in ESTIA despite the fact that it is addressed to asylum-seekers. At the end of 2018, 5,649 beneficiaries of international protection were provided accommodation in apartments through ESTIA and 11,000 received cash assistance. This agreement on the transitional period was made mostly due to the fact that the next step for the housing of recognised refugees, or integration measures in general, was not prepared from the part of the state. More specifically, the HELIOS integration programme that would provide housing to refugees was not yet active in order to include recognised refugees.

In 12 March 2019 and still in the absence of the next integration step that could address the housing needs of refugees, a Ministerial Decision 6382/2019 was issued by the Ministry of Migration Policy to regulate the ESTIA scheme. This Ministerial Decision provided details on the preconditions and deadlines regarding the accommodation of asylum-seekers and recognised refugees. More specifically, those already benefiting from the ESTIA scheme as asylum-seekers would be provided accommodation for another 6 months after the notification of the asylum decision, while in cases of families with children this period could be extended until the end of the current school year. In cases of extremely vulnerable recognised refugees, such as pregnant women and women up to two months after giving birth or people suffering from very serious health conditions, accommodation could be extended beyond 6 months after recognition. Despite these exceptions, a large number of refugees were forced to leave their apartments. The first group of beneficiaries of international protection required to leave their accommodation were those recognised before the end of July 2017, and the deadline given for their departure was the 31st of March 2019. A total of 204 recognised refugees who had been granted protection 20 months ago and accommodated under the ESTIA scheme were requested to leave their apartments by the end of March 2019; since then, more recognised refugees have been forced to abandon the ESTIA scheme.

Serious concerns have been expressed through press releases regarding these evictions of refugees in Greece, and a variety of reports urge the Greek authorities to adhere to their obligations under international, EU and national legislation and ensure

⁵ For a detailed description of different kinds of social benefits in Greece, for both vulnerable Greeks and recognized refugees, see: <https://bit.ly/2QDcjE2>

the minimum of a dignified and secure living of refugees (RSA, 2019b). Additionally, NGO workers have been on strike in response to this since March 2019, noting that this development will leave newly recognised refugees homeless and unable to survive (NGO Workers Union, 2019).

Driven Reforms

Following the results of the European elections, Greek national and regional elections were held on the 7th of July 2019, leading to the victory of right-wing party New Democracy (ND). The return to power of the conservatives in Greece marked the beginning of a new era for the country. The newly elected government, as it had promised, promptly proceeded with several reforms in the country's policies. Among others, the government announced new robust policy measures of immediate action regarding migration in order to deal with the increased flows, the overcrowding in the North-eastern Aegean islands, the increase of asylum applications, as well as the lack of capacity in reception facilities.

On the 30th of September 2019, the Greek government announced its intention to present a bill regarding asylum legislation in Greece. According to the relevant press release, this bill would expressly aim at "restricting the framework for requesting and granting asylum", "ending anarchy", remedying the "unstructured Greek asylum system" and eradicating the consequences of legislation adopted by the previous government (RSA, 2019a). Additionally, the same press release noted that "based on the analysis of statistics on nationalities of persons arriving in the country, it is our common understanding that this is a migration and not a refugee issue." (General Secretariat of Information and Communication, 2019). As such, the government considers that the "profile of the refugee" should be applied only to Syrians and claims that the majority of newcomers are economic migrants. It has also announced its intention to increase returns "from 1,806 in the 4.5 years of SYRIZA governance to 10,000 by the end of 2020".

On the 15th of October 2019, the Ministry of Citizen Protection published the International Protection Bill and submitted it to public consultation until the 21st of October 2019 (MOPOCP, 2019b). Several humanitarian actors reacted against the limited timeframe of the public consultation and published press releases denouncing that it is impossible to comment on the substance of the bill in such a short notice and that the public consultation unfortunately served as a fig leaf. Moreover, humanitarian actors reported that the proposed draft bill leads to the blatant undermining of fundamental guarantees and rights of refugees and asylum seekers in violation of international, EU and national law, as well as of the principle of non-refoulement (GCR, 2019).

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

This report is part of the third Work Package of RESPOND and deals with the issues of refugee protection and asylum procedures. By the term “refugee protection” we referred to the ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors concerned with defining, conceptualising and implementing the asylum and refugee protection in the EU Member States. The report analysed both the legal framework on refugee protection and the relevant implementation issues.

Regarding the legal framework on asylum procedure and refugee protection, significant recent developments were presented in the relevant section entitled “Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework”. Starting from Law 3907/2011 that established for the first time the Asylum Service, the First Reception Service and the Appeals Authority, the increase in refugee arrivals followed by the EU-Turkey Statement of the 18th of March 2016 and the adoption of Law 4375/2016. Asylum applications in Greece increased significantly due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands where Hotspots are established and where crucial protection issues are on a rise until today. The relevant chapter focused on the following themes: Asylum procedures; The criteria for recognition and the rights of refugees, those eligible for subsidiary protection and applicants for international protection; Reception and Identification Centres and the geographical restriction on the eastern Aegean islands; Registration and Detention.

The chapter entitled “Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions” was based on existing practices and responses at the grassroots level. It has thus drawn from the gathered empirical research evidence and, more specifically, from the interviews with refugees and actors involved in the field (micro and meso level). In this chapter, we reflected on the implementation of refugee protection by focusing on the following themes: Access to the asylum procedure for new arrivals; Moria Hotspot living conditions; Registration Procedures and the example of Lesbos island; Asylum Procedures (Transformations in Second instance; The Family Reunification application process; The impact of the EU-Turkey Statement; The upgrade of the role of EASO in the National Asylum Procedures and the cooperation with GAS); Access to information and Legal assistance; Detention; and Protection issues for recognised refugees.

Significant observations emerge from this analysis, as specific challenges remain and give rise to protection and safety risks. The aforementioned transformations in legislation led to a considerable increase in asylum applications in Greece due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands where Hotspots were established. The recently introduced “Fast-Track Border Procedure” does not seem to facilitate the acceleration of the asylum applications. Instead, living conditions in the RICs (the Hotspots in the Eastern Aegean islands) are worsening due to the overcrowding and the inadequate protection facilities and services. Considering refugee protection not merely as an institutional protection in accordance to the relevant laws but also as the obligation for the provision of full and equal respect for their human rights and coverage of their basic human needs, survival and physical security, we consider the Hotspot system and the issues emerging from the EU-Turkey

Statement as a regime that intensely threatens refugee protection. Drawing from the field research conducted, the reception and living conditions also raise serious concerns regarding the protection of refugees, as their basic needs and human rights are threatened and violated on an everyday basis.

Except for the insufficient living conditions forced upon asylum seekers residing in the North-eastern Aegean islands, there is still a serious lack of security and provisions in terms of supporting services providing medical and psychosocial support, information regarding the asylum procedures and the rights of an asylum-seeker and, of course, legal aid and legal representation. The interviews with refugees revealed that the majority did not have enough information in order to understand the legal processes they should follow. The same observations also apply to the importance of other procedures, such as the vulnerability assessment, as refugees are usually not officially informed on the significance of this procedure. Instead, in some cases they manage to gather information from their networks, either from community leaders or other refugees residing in the Hotspot facilities, a fact that highlights the crucial importance of informal support and counselling.

Additionally, the expansion of the role of EASO from assessing vulnerability, conducting interviews and drafting opinions in border procedures to similar competencies in the regular asylum procedure – was considered by most interviewees as a negative development. Furthermore, most interviewees commonly report bad experiences, mainly with EASO but also with other relevant stakeholders in the field. The violation of gender and religious rights during the procedures was also mentioned, especially by women who were forced to be photographed and fingerprinted without their hijab. A number of other serious concerns emerged from the analysis provided regarding protection issues while in detention. It should also be mentioned that we faced serious difficulties and obstacles in collecting information and data regarding the implementation of administrative detention, policies and living conditions in Lesvos pre-removal centre, as well as returns and readmissions.

Furthermore, we observed a wide range of differentiations regarding the overall implementation of refugee protection and asylum procedures. On the one hand, there are differences between the legal frameworks applied to those who arrive through the land borders of Evros and those who arrive through the North-eastern Aegean islands; this is a matter of fact determined in terms of distinctions set by legislation. Nevertheless, on the other hand, there are differentiations in the implementation of one same legal framework (e.g. for those who arrive through the North-eastern Aegean islands) depending on the site, point in time and work of different actors. Beyond the provisions of the relevant laws, a wide range of internal official actors (such as the police) issue instructions that determine the emergence of a variety of policies and practices which differ from one site and RIC to another, constantly change in time and are not defined in legislation.

Concluding this report, it is important to remind the shifting Greek political context at the time of its writing. To the extent that a wide range of conservative measures on refugee issues have been mostly announced but also implemented, the issues of refugee protection and asylum procedure in Greece are considered to be under

transition and transformation, once again highlighting the crucially temporary and fluid character of the examined issues.

Table 1: Policy Recommendations

- Full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and spirit of human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law. Assurance that the human rights of all migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees are the primary consideration of all negotiations.
- End of the EU “Hotspot Approach” and respect of the right to live in dignity.
- End of the geographical restriction and facilitation of the transfer of asylum-seekers from the North-eastern Aegean islands to the mainland.
- Significant increase in accommodation facilities both in the mainland and in the North-eastern Aegean islands.
- Promotion of viable alternatives to detention by developing open, sustainable and safe reception infrastructures for migrants, asylum-seekers and beneficiaries of international protection and suitable accommodation for vulnerable groups.
- Except for the guarantee of survival and physical security, there is an urgent need for an international protection system that will respect the rights of all individuals and develop clear procedural and legislative safeguards to protect human rights and guarantee the protection of vulnerable individuals and persons in danger.
- Free access to legal counselling and representation. On-time legal advice, preferably through personal contact with assigned caseworkers and lawyers.
- Assurance that procedural guarantees, including access to legal representation and legal aid in decisions surrounding any deprivation of liberty, are fully implemented.
- Assurance of the non-detention of vulnerable groups, including children, in line with the guidance of the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child.
- Screening of individual cases of all detained persons.
- Significant increase in the capacity of Reception and Identification Centres.
- Significant increase in the Capacity of the Asylum Service.
- Relevant, appropriate and increased use of interpreters.
- Better identification of persons with special needs, including potential asylum-seekers requiring referral to appropriate services.
- Improvement in the coordination between relevant governmental and non-governmental actors dealing with international protection.

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Appendices

Figure 1. Asylum Procedure in the context of the EU-Turkey Statement.

Notes: If at any point there is a withdrawal of application or rejective decision not appealed, it leads to end of procedure.

Source: Asylum Service, <https://bit.ly/2o7cewG>.

Overview of the legal framework

Table 2: Main legislative acts relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions, detention and content of protection

Title (EN)	Original Title (GR)	Abbreviation	Web Link
<p>Law 4375/2016 “Organization and functioning of the Asylum Service, Appeals Authority, Reception and Identification Service, establishment of General Secretariat for Reception, transposition of Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council ‘on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (recast)’ (L 180/29.6.2013), provisions on employment of beneficiaries of international protection” and other provisions. Gazette 51/A/3-4-2016</p> <p><i>Amended by:</i> Law 4399/2016, Gazette 117/A/22-6-2016 <i>Amended by:</i> Law 4461/2017, Gazette 38/A/28-3-2017 <i>Amended by:</i> Law 4485/2017, Gazette 114/A/4-8-2017 <i>Amended by:</i> Law 4540/2018, Gazette 91/A/22-5-2018</p>	<p>Νόμος 4375/2016 «Οργάνωση και λειτουργία Υπηρεσίας Ασύλου, Αρχής Προσφυγών, Υπηρεσίας Υποδοχής και Ταυτοποίησης σύσταση Γενικής Γραμματείας Υποδοχής, προσαρμογή της Ελληνικής Νομοθεσίας προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 2013/32/ΕΕ του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου «σχετικά με τις κοινές διαδικασίες για τη χορήγηση και ανάκληση του καθεστώτος διεθνούς προστασίας (αναδιατύπωση)» (L 180/29.6.2013), διατάξεις για την εργασία δικαιούχων διεθνούς προστασίας και άλλες διατάξεις. ΦΕΚ 51/A/3-4-2016</p> <p><i>Τροπ.:</i> Νόμος 4399/2016, ΦΕΚ 117/A/22-6-2016 <i>Τροπ.:</i> Νόμος 4461/2017, ΦΕΚ 38/A/28-3-2017 <i>Τροπ.:</i> Νόμος 4485/2017, ΦΕΚ 114/A/4-8-2017 <i>Τροπ.:</i> Νόμος 4540/2018, ΦΕΚ 91/A/22-5-2018</p>	<p>L 4375/2016 (Asylum Act)</p>	<p>http://bit.ly/2Kkm2cu (EN) http://bit.ly/234vUhP (GR)</p> <p>http://bit.ly/2IKABdD (GR) http://bit.ly/2y0vNq5 (GR) http://bit.ly/2FLLM3H (GR) https://bit.ly/2KCbDx6 (GR)</p>
<p>Law 4540/2018 “Transposition of Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast, L 180/96/29.6.2013) and other provisions... Amendment of asylum procedures and other provisions” Gazette 91/A/22-5-2018</p>	<p>Νόμος 4540/2018 «Προσαρμογή της ελληνικής νομοθεσίας προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 2013/33/ΕΕ του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου της 26ης Ιουνίου 2013, σχετικά με τις απαιτήσεις για την υποδοχή των αιτούντων διεθνή προστασία (αναδιατύπωση, L 180/96/29.6.2013) και άλλες διατάξεις - Τροποποίηση του ν. 4251/2014 (Α' 80) για την προσαρμογή της ελληνικής νομοθεσίας στην Οδηγία 2014/66/ΕΕ της 15ης Μαΐου 2014 του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου σχετικά με τις προϋποθέσεις εισόδου και διαμονής υπηκόων τρίτων χωρών στο πλαίσιο ενδοεταίρικης μετάθεσης - Τροποποίηση διαδικασιών ασύλου και άλλες διατάξεις»</p>	<p>L 4540/2018 (Reception Act)</p>	<p>https://bit.ly/2KCbDx6 (GR)</p>

<p>Law 3907/2011 "on the establishment of an Asylum Service and a First Reception Service, transposition into Greek legislation of Directive 2008/115/EC "on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third country nationals" and other provisions. Gazette 7/A/26-01-2011</p> <p>Amended by: Presidential Decree 133/2013, Gazette 198/A/25-09-2013 Law 4058/2012, Gazette 63/A/22-03-2012 Law 4375/2016, Gazette 51/A/3-4-2016</p>	<p>Νόμος 3907/2011 «1δρυση Υπηρεσίας Ασύλου και Υπηρεσίας Πρώτης Υποδοχής, προσαρμογή της ελληνικής νομοθεσίας προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 2008/115/ΕΚ «σχετικά με τους κοινούς κανόνες και διαδικασίες στα κράτη-μέλη για την επιστροφή των παρανόμως διαμενόντων υπηκόων τρίτων χωρών» και λοιπές διατάξεις» ΦΕΚ 7/A/26-01-2011</p> <p>Τροποποίηση από: Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 133/2013, ΦΕΚ 198/A/25-09-2013 Νόμος 4058/2012, ΦΕΚ 63/A/22-03-2012 Νόμος 4375/2016, ΦΕΚ 51/A/3-4-2016</p>	<p>L 3907/2011</p> <p>PD 133/2013 L 4058/2012 L 4375/2016</p>	<p>http://bit.ly/1KHa9dV (EN)</p> <p>http://bit.ly/1GfXFJ2 (GR) http://bit.ly/1FoiWx (GR) http://bit.ly/234vUhp (GR)</p>
<p>Presidential Decree 114/2010 "on the establishment of a single procedure for granting the status of refugee or of beneficiary of subsidiary protection to aliens or to stateless persons in conformity with Council Directive 2005/85/EC on minimum standards on procedures in Member States for granting and withdrawing refugee status" Gazette 195/A/22-11-2010</p> <p>Amended by: Presidential Decree 116/2012, Gazette 201/A/19-10-2012 Presidential Decree 113/2013, Gazette 146/A/14-06-2013 Presidential Decree 167/2014, Gazette 252/A/01-12-2014 Law 4375/2016, Gazette 51/A/3-4-2016</p>	<p>Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 114/2010 «Καθιέρωση ενιαίας διαδικασίας αναγνώρισης σε αλλοδαπούς και ανιθαγενείς του καθεστώτος του πρόσφυγα ή δικαιούχου επικουρικής προστασίας σε συμμόρφωση προς την Οδηγία 2005/85/ΕΚ του Συμβουλίου "σχετικά με τις ελάχιστες προδιαγραφές για τις διαδικασίες με τις οποίες τα κράτη μέλη χορηγούν και ανακαλούν το καθεστώς του πρόσφυγα», ΦΕΚ 195/A/22-11-2010</p> <p>Τροποποίηση από: Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 116/2012, ΦΕΚ 201/A/19-10-2012 Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 113/2013, ΦΕΚ 146/A/14-06-2013 Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 167/2014, ΦΕΚ 252/A/01-12-2014 Νόμος 4375/2016, ΦΕΚ 51/A/3-4-2016</p>	<p>PD 114/2010 (Old Procedure Decree)</p> <p>PD 116/2012 PD 113/2013 PD 167/2014 L 4375/2016</p>	<p>http://bit.ly/1LWAO3C (EN)</p> <p>http://bit.ly/1GfXCwV (EN) http://bit.ly/1M36apZ (EN) http://bit.ly/1ENgV9B (GR) http://bit.ly/1ct2sZY (GR) http://bit.ly/234vUhp (GR)</p>
<p>Presidential Decree 141/2013 "on the transposition into the Greek legislation of Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 (L 337) on minimum standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection and for the content of the protection granted (recast)" Gazette 226/A/21-10-2013</p>	<p>Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 141/2013 «Προσαρμογή της ελληνικής νομοθεσίας προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 2011/95/ΕΕ του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου της 13ης Δεκεμβρίου 2011 (L 337) σχετικά με τις απαιτήσεις για την αναγνώριση και το καθεστώς των αλλοδαπών ή των ανιθαγενών ως δικαιούχων διεθνούς προστασίας, για ένα ενιαίο καθεστώς για τους πρόσφυγες ή για τα άτομα που δικαιούνται επικουρική προστασία και για το περιεχόμενο της παρεχόμενης προστασίας (αναδιατύπωση)», ΦΕΚ 226/A/21-10-2013</p>	<p>PD 141/2013 (Qualification Decree)</p>	<p>http://bit.ly/2lbV4aM (GR)</p>

Presidential Decree 220/2007 on the transposition into the Greek legislation of Council Directive 2003/9/EC from January 27, 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers Gazette 251/A/13-11-2007	Προσαρμογή της Ελληνικής Νομοθεσίας προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 2003/9/ΕΚ του Συμβουλίου της 27ης Ιανουαρίου 2003, σχετικά με τις ελάχιστες απαιτήσεις για την υποδοχή των αιτούντων άσυλο στα κράτη μέλη, ΦΕΚ 251/A/13-11-2007	PD 220/2007 (Reception Decree)	http://bit.ly/2llMseP (GR)
Law 4251/2014 “Immigration and Social Integration Code and other provisions” Gazette 80/A/01-04-2014 Amended by: Law 4332/2015, Gazette 76/A/09-07-2015 Amended by: Law 4540/2018, Gazette 91/A/22-5-2018	Νόμος 4251/2014 «Κώδικας Μετανάστευσης και Κοινωνικής Ένταξης και λοιπές διατάξεις» ΦΕΚ 80/A/01-04-2014 Τροπ: Νόμος 4332/2015, ΦΕΚ 76/A/09-07-2015 Τροπ.: Νόμος 4540/2018, ΦΕΚ 91/A/22-5-2018	Immigration Code L 4332/2015	http://bit.ly/1F0uxp0 (GR) http://bit.ly/1LfUfDB (GR) https://bit.ly/2KCbDx6 (GR)
Law 3386/2005 “Entry, Residence and Social Integration of Third Country Nationals on the Greek Territory” Abolished by: Law 4251/2014 except for Articles 76, 77, 78, 80, 81, 82, 83, 89(1)-(3) Amended by: Law 4332/2015	Νόμος 3386/2005 «Είσοδος, διαμονή και κοινωνική ένταξη υπηκόων τρίτων χωρών στην Ελληνική Επικράτεια» Καταργήθηκε από: Νόμος 4251/2014 πλην των διατάξεων των άρθρων 76, 77, 78, 80, 81, 82, 83, 89 παρ. 1-3 Τροπ.: Νόμος 4332/2015	L 3386/2005	http://bit.ly/1Pps1eO (EN) http://bit.ly/1Qkzh9R (GR)
Law 4554/2018 “Guardianship of unaccompanied children and other provisions” Gazette 130/A/18-7-2018	Νόμος 4554/2018 «Επιτροπεία ασυνόδευτων ανηλίκων και άλλες διατάξεις», ΦΕΚ 130/A/18-7-2018	L 4554/2018	https://bit.ly/2FAeL7z (GR)
Presidential Decree 131/2006 on the transposition of Directive 2003/86/EC on the right to family reunification Gazette 143/A/13-7-2006 Amended by: PD 167/2008, PD 113/2013	Προεδρικό Διάταγμα 131/2006 Εναρμόνιση της ελληνικής νομοθεσίας με την Οδηγία 2003/86/ΕΚ σχετικά με το δικαίωμα οικογενειακής επανένωσης, ΦΕΚ 143/A/13-7-2006 Τροπ: ΠΔ 167/2008, ΠΔ 113/2013	PD 131/2006 (Family Reunification Decree)	http://bit.ly/2nHCPOu (GR)

Source: AIDA (Asylum Information Database) (2019) Country Reports: Greece. 2018 Update. [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/2OGULnP> [Accessed 15 September 2019]

Table 3: Main implementing decrees and administrative guidelines and regulations relevant to asylum procedures, reception conditions, detention and content of protection

Title (EN)	Original Title (GR)	Abbreviation	Web Link
Joint Ministerial Decision οικ. 13257/2016 on the implementation of the special border procedure (Article 60(4) L 4375/2016) Gazette B/3455/26.10.2016	Κοινή Υπουργική Απόφαση οικ. 13257/2016: Εφαρμογή των διατάξεων της παραγράφου 4 του άρθρου 60 του Ν. 4375/2016 (Α' 51), ΦΕΚ Β/3455/26.10.2016	Fast-Track Border Procedure JMD	http://bit.ly/2maKUeC (GR)
Joint Ministerial Decision οικ. 12205 on the provision of legal aid to applicants for international protection Gazette B/2864/9-9-2016	Κοινή Υπουργική Απόφαση οικ. 12205: Παροχή νομικής συνδρομής σε αιτούντες διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/2864/9-9-2016	Legal Aid JMD	http://bit.ly/2kPSjzE (GR)
Joint Ministerial Decision 1982/2016 on age assessment of applicants for international protection Gazette B/335/16-2-2016	Κοινή Υπουργική Απόφαση 1982/2016 διαπίστωση ανηλικότητας των αιτούντων διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/335/16-2-2016	Age Assessment JMD	http://bit.ly/2lc8mDX (GR)
Decision οικ. 868/2018 of the Director of the Asylum Service on the duration of international protection applicants' cards Gazette B/201/30.01.2018	Απόφαση αριθμ. οικ. 868/2018 της Διευθύντριας Υπηρεσίας Ασύλου: Διάρκεια ισχύος δελτίων αιτούντων διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/201/30.01.2018	Asylum Seeker Card Decision	http://bit.ly/2DEDtka (GR)
Decision οικ. 8269/2018 of the Director of the Asylum Service on restriction of movement of applicants for international protection Gazette B/1366/20.04.2018	Απόφαση αριθμ. οικ. 8269/2018 του Διευθυντή Υπηρεσίας Ασύλου: Περιορισμός κυκλοφορίας των αιτούντων διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/1366/20.04.2018	Restriction of Movement Decision	https://bit.ly/2NrYgO4 (GR)
Decision οικ. 18984/2018 of the Director of the Asylum Service on restriction of movement of applicants for international protection Gazette B/4427/05.10.2018	Απόφαση αριθμ. οικ. 18984/2018 του Διευθυντή Υπηρεσίας Ασύλου: Περιορισμός κυκλοφορίας των αιτούντων διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/4427/05.10.2018	Restriction of Movement Decision	https://bit.ly/2QDDmkn (GR)
Joint Ministerial Decision οικ. 10566 on the procedure for issuing travel documents to beneficiaries of and applicants for international protection Gazette B/3223/2-12-2014	Κοινή Υπουργική Απόφαση οικ. 10566 Διαδικασία χορήγησης ταξιδιωτικών εγγράφων σε δικαιούχους διεθνούς προστασίας, καθώς και στους αιτούντες διεθνή προστασία, ΦΕΚ Β/3223/2-12-2014	Travel Documents JMD	http://bit.ly/2mfwqXA (GR)
Joint Ministerial Decision 7315/2014 on the procedure for granting residence permits to beneficiaries of international protection Gazette B/2461/16-9-2014	Κοινή Υπουργική Απόφαση 7315/29.8.2014 Διαδικασία χορήγησης ΑΔΕΤ στους δικαιούχους διεθνούς προστασίας, ΦΕΚ Β/2461/16-9-2014	Residence Permits JMD	http://bit.ly/2o6rTuM (GR)
Hellenic Police Circular 1604/17/681730 on participation of applicants for international protection in voluntary repatriation programmes of the International Organisation for Migration (IOM)	Εγκύκλιος Ελληνικής Αστυνομίας 1604/17/681730 Συμμετοχή αλλοδαπών υπηκόων αιτούντων τη χορήγηση καθεστώτος διεθνούς προστασίας στα προγράμματα οικειοθελούς επαναπατριsmού του Διεθνούς Οργανισμού Μετανάστευσης (Δ.Ο.Μ.)		http://bit.ly/2E8MImr (GR)

Source: AIDA (Asylum Information Database) (2019) Country Reports: Greece. 2018 Update. [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/2OGULnP> [Accessed 15 September 2019]

Table 4. Micro-level interviewees: Pseudonyms and personal information

Micro-level Interviews							
Pseudonyms	Age	Civic status	Date of arrival in Greece	Gender	Legal status	Nationality	Point of Arrival in Greece
Kingslot	25	Single	07/2016	M	subsidiary protection	Afghan, Born & Raised in Pakistan	Lesvos
Ahmed	32	Married with family	Not Applicable	M	Asylum Seeker	Palestinian, Born and lived in Syria	Lesvos
Amin	27	Single	11/2015	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan, Born & Raised in Iran	Kos
Abdul	26	Engaged in Afghanistan	04/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Lesvos
Syrian Refugee	18	Single	Not Applicable	F	Applicant for Family Reunification	Syrian	Lesvos
Aynla	20	Single	04/2018	M	subsidiary protection	Somalia	Lesvos
Izzy	25	Not Applicable	10/2008	M	Asylum Seeker	Afgan	Lesvos
Jasmid	28	In a relationship	2008	M	subsidiary protection	Afgan, Born & Raised in Iran	Lesvos
Libeex	24	Single	2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Somalia	Lesvos
Michael	35	In a relationship	04/2008	M	Asylum Seeker	Sudan	Lesvos
Mohammad	18	Single	12/2016	M	International Protection	Syrian	Lesvos
Nam & Mohammad	45 & 32	Married with family	09/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Iraq	Lesvos
Ermis	18	Single	03/2016	M	Applicant for Family Reunification	Afghan, Born & Raised in Iran	Lesvos
Penen		Not Applicable	05/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Congo	Lesvos
Ramon	22	Single	10/2016	M	Asylum Seeker	Born in Afghanistan, lived in Pakistan & Iran	Chios
Thanasis-Mah	23	Single	2016, before the EU-Turkey Deal	M	International Protection	Afghan, Raised in Iran	Chios
Wael	20	Single	10/2015	M	Refugee-Residence permit	Syrian	Lesvos
William	18	Single	07/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Burundi	Lesvos
Willy	24	Single	1/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Cameroon	Lesvos

Arif & Nemen	30 & 24	Married with 2 children	07/2017	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Kastelorizo & Kos
Mohsin & Lima	26 & 21	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Syrians	Alexandroupolis
Medin & Farus	23 & 23	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Lesvos
Hafiz & Banek	29 & 23	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Alexandroupolis
Anonymus	32	Single	2009	M	International Protection	Afghan, Lived some years in Iran	Lesvos
Antoine	31	Single	06/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Guinea	Lesvos
Fatima	24	Single	11/2017	F	Asylum Seeker	Afghan, Lived in Pakistan	Lesvos
Faz	21	Single	30/03/2016	M	Not Applicable	Iran	Lesvos
Jack	21	Single	03/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Iraq	Lesvos
Costas	37	Married with family in Russia	06/2013	M	Asylum Seeker	Burundi	Lesvos
Robel	24	Single	09/2017	M	Asylum Seeker, applied for 2nd instance	Eritrea	Lesvos
Seralam	26	Single	06/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Alexandroupolis
Group Interview	1.34, 2.23, 3.16, 4.23, 5.55	1.2.5. Married with family, 3.4. Married together	Unassigned	1.2.3.5. M., 4. F	Asylum Seekers	1.Afghan, 2. Pakistan, 3.4. Iran, 5. Iraq	Lesvos
Norouh	21	Single	Unassigned	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Lesvos
Rehma	48	Single	08/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Syrian	Lesvos

Table 5. Questions to interviewees from the meso level during the semi-structured interviews

1. What do you think about the current provisions in refugee protection in Greece, such as access to Greece, access to asylum procedure and access to safe places etc.?
 - Are they well established and offer a good standard of protection for different needs? If not, what are the main problems/challenges of these provisions?
 - How is the access to the asylum procedure being structured? Are there any forms of pre-selection (Admissibility checks, vulnerability criteria, “prospect to stay”? Which groups are being excluded on which grounds) taking place, by whom? How is it possible to secure “protection” under these circumstances?
2. Does your work relate to “relocation” and “resettlement” and family reunification? If so, how does it relate to your understanding of protection?
3. What is your experience with the Dublin regulation and the return practice? Do protection-arguments play a role in it?
4. What is your experience with the deportation and return policy? Did it change since 2015 (or earlier for certain countries) and in which sense? Do protection arguments play a role in it?
 - Are there legal provisions to complain against a deportation order – and in practice? Are there any bans/stops on deportation to certain countries? Is there any kind of monitoring taking place?
5. What is your experience with detention? How is it organized (who gets detained on which grounds, where and how long the maximum stay is?)
 - Who is running detention camps and prisons? Do protection arguments play a role in it? Do lawyers and human rights groups have access? Is there the possibility to access the asylum procedure within detention?
 - What happens with the people after the maximum stay?
6. Based on your experiences, is the current protection regime in need of reform in Greece? If so, in which way and how?
 - Which bodies (national, local state, EU, etc.) should be responsible for the protection of refugees and asylum seekers in your view?

Table 6. Questions to interviewees from the micro level during the semi-structured interviews

- Did you participate in any registration and/or asylum procedures? If so, can you describe the whole registration and asylum application procedure? Who asked you to do what and when? If you did not participate in procedures, was it because you did not want to or you had no possibility to do so? Are you aware about your rights and obligations as an asylum seeker?
- Were your expectations about the asylum process met or did you find it to be more or less difficult than expected? How easy was it for you to apply for asylum?
- How did you experience the procedures? What was your impression of the officers' behaviour during the procedure? Did they pay attention to your needs or to the needs of other people that you know (in particular, needs in terms of gender, age or illness)?
- What is the status of your registration and/or asylum application right now? Did you (or do you) have enough information (written or oral) in a language that you understand? Did you (or do you) know how long the procedure would take? Did you (or do you) know what you could do in case of a negative decision or a decision that does not satisfy you (e.g. the difference between subsidiary status instead of refugee status)?
- Between your arrival and the decision on your asylum application, did you encounter any support in terms of legal advice, childcare, language classes, place to live, etc.? If so, who provided the support? Please, elaborate a little on how your most basic needs were met.
- Are any of your family members staying in other countries than your home country? If so, have you tried to re-unite with them? If so, did you get assistance with this? What was the outcome?
- Have you experienced transfer to (another) EU country or to Turkey, e.g. because you applied for asylum somewhere else first? If so, was it voluntary or obligatory for you? What did it look like? Did you know why, where and when you would be transferred? Were you detained before or afterwards? Were you escorted or assisted to the border or from the border? How did you make your way (back) to [country] after that?
- Have you been issued a return order / decision on deportation? If so, could you do anything to cancel this order / decision? Were you assisted by anyone in executing or cancelling the return order (IOM, NGOs, free legal advice)?
- Did you experience detention (or administrative detention)? For how long? How have you been treated, by whom? Did you have any information on your legal possibilities and remedies, by whom? Did you have access to a lawyer?